

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D3.8 Report on results of the lab trials and of the operational readiness for field trials v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5th generation
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ASC	Assisted Service Continuity
BO2BO	Back Office to Back Office
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAV	Connected Autonomous Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CPM	Cooperative Perception Message
CST	Critical and Secured Transportations
DbW	Drive By Wire
DL	DownLoad
E2E	End-to-End
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FT	Field Trial
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
gNB	Next Generation NodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HD	High-Definition
IF	Integration Fabric
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet Of Things
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAN	Local Area Network
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LT	Lab Trial
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MEC2BO	MEC to Back Office
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator

MPC	Model-predictive control
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NAT	Network Address Translation
NB-IoT	NarrowBand Internet of Things
NDT	Normal Distributions Transform
NFC	Near Field Communications
NLOS	Non-Line-Of-Sight
NR	New Radio
NTP	Network Time Protocol
NSA	Non-Standalone
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On Board Unit
OSM	Open Source MANO
PI	Performance Indicator
PID	Proportional-integral-derivative (control)
PPS	Pulse-per-second
PRAE	Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X Related Network Functions enabler
RAN	Radio Access Network
ROS	Robot Operating System
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
RTMP	Real-Time Messaging Protocol
RTSP	Real-Time Streaming Protocol
RTT	Round Trip Time
SA	Standalone
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SPATEM	Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message
SQL	Structured Query Language
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TMS	Transport Management System
TWP	Tenant Web Portal
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
UL	UpLoad
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2BO	Vehicle to Back Office
V2MEC	Vehicle to MEC
V2P	Vehicle-to-pedestrian
V2x	Vehicle-to-everything

VCU	Vehicle Computing Unit
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VR	Virtual Reality
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network

Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM (Connected and Automated Mobility) applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki), spanning across 3 EU member states' borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G end-to-end interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways and shipways throughout Europe [1].

5G-ROUTES planned three iterative and consecutive testing cycles each lasting for about 6 months, preceded by relevant setup/preparation and lab trial periods, and followed by corresponding parallel evaluation and/or re-design/upgrade improvement periods to ensure a smooth and aligned evolution of the validations in the field trials. The first set of field trials was planned to be performed 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) networks, and the following trials in 5G Standalone (SA) Release 16 networks, with deployments of different versions of the CAM Services Platform, which is developed in 5G-ROUTES.

The scope of this deliverable is to report on the results of the first lab trial period, which precedes the 5G NSA field trials. During the first set of lab trials, the CAM Services Platform was still under deployment, and only two enablers were deployed: the V2X (Vehicle to everything) broker (VTT) and the Tenant Web Portal (EBOS). These enablers were deployed on the cloud. The purpose of the lab trials was to assure that the use cases are ready for the planned 5G NSA field trials. The different components of the use cases were integrated locally at the sites of the developing partners, and tests were mainly performed at the facilities of the developers or in nearby 5G NSA test sites, to which they have access. Hence, most of the tests were performed in single network environments, with as main focus to test whether the use cases perform as expected, and whether the target KPIs in the field trials can be achieved.

In addition, cross-border handover tests were performed at the virtual cross-border site in Bikernieki. In order to avoid issues related to the connection of the 5G modem to the test networks in the field trial sites, the partners have agreed to use the same modem for the majority of the use cases. As modem the Mikrotik 5G router has been selected, which has been tested extensively in the Bikernieki virtual border site. Cross-border tests were performed for two use cases (UC3.2 and UC3.3) in May 2023, and are reported in this report.

The deliverable reports for each use case on the lab trials performed in order to assess the functioning and performance of the respective use case, as well as on the field trial readiness verification. The lab trials were performed mainly near the facilities of the developers. For field trial readiness verification, a checklist is used, for assuring that the use case is ready to be evaluated at the field trials. The checklist addresses the operation of the different components (vehicles, On-Board Units (OBUs), external servers, infrastructure sensors, other end-user devices like smartphones), the CAM services, the integration with the enablers, and the 5G network at the field trial sites. The tests for the checklist were mainly performed by the use case leaders, and the Estonian and Latvian MNOs verified the operation of the networks at the trial sites.

By assuring that the use case works locally, and that cross-border behaviour is supported for similar use cases and the user equipment (UE) which is used in the use case, the use cases are ready to go to the field trials.

The lab trial tests were performed during the first half of 2022, and the report was written in June 2022.

Following the feedback from the European Commission and the reviewers in May 2022, the project was refocused during Summer 2022, and consequently the planned 5G NSA trials were not performed, whereas some of the use cases were discarded. This report gives the status of the work done on the use cases prior to the refocusing. Work is reported according to the original use case structure, which is described in D1.1.

Table 1 gives an overview of the readiness of the use cases for the field trials. In June 2022, not all the components, which were needed to execute and evaluate the use cases in the field trials, were ready. The 5G test networks in Valga-Valka and Muuga-Vuosaari were still under test or being developed at the end of June. Some functionalities of the Tenant Web Portal, such as the automated transfer of logging data were still under

development. At the first submission of the report in the Summer of 2022, the completion rate was 70%. The completion rate for the readiness for the planned 5G NSA trials has been reviewed in September 2023. Due to the refocusing, use cases UC3.2, UC5.3 and UC2.2 were discontinued, and use cases UC3.3 and UC5.2 were redesigned.

When reviewing the completion rate for 5G NSA tests (Table 1), the integration with the CAM Services Platform (which is only used for the 5G SA tests) has not been taken into account. Table 1 shows the readiness for 5G NSA field trials. Aspects which are still under development in September 2023 are related to the integration of the logging (i.e., automated starting and stopping of logging at experiments, allowing to harmonise the timing of the logs at different devices an automated upload of the logs at the end of the experiments) and have not yet been tested. Issues which still not be integrated further by the use cases mainly relate to logging (such as the synchronisation of the different data) and the integration with the enablers.

Table 1. Overview of the 5G NSA field trial readiness completion for the use cases

Group	UC1.1	UC1.2	UC1.3	UC2.1	UC2.2	UC3.1	UC3.2	UC3.3	UC4.1	UC4.2	UC5.1	UC5.2	UC5.3
Vehicle related issues	94 %	100 %	100 %		89 %	100 %	100 %	100 %			79 %		33 %
OBU related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %		70 %	100 %	81 %	100 %			65 %	33 %	
Infrastructure related issues				71 %									
External servers	92 %	92 %		50 %	83 %		100 %	100 %		100 %	58 %	0 %	83 %
Other end user devices								100 %	83 %	83 %	29 %	31 %	
Subtotal: user device related issues	96 %	98 %	100 %	62 %	80 %	100 %	92 %	100 %	83 %	92 %	58 %	21 %	67 %
CAM services			100 %						100 %			0 %	
Privacy and security issues			100 %	0 %			0 %			100 %	25 %		0 %
Subtotal: Use case specific	96 %	98 %	100 %	64 %	80 %	100 %	87 %	100 %	92 %	92 %	56 %	15 %	60 %
Tenant Web Portal	81 %	81 %	71 %	50 %	50 %	75 %	50 %	88 %	71 %	63 %	50 %	50 %	57 %
V2X router				10 %		100 %		80 %					
Subtotal_ Enabler related issues	81 %	81 %	71 %	35 %	50 %	83 %	50 %	85 %	71 %	63 %	50 %	50 %	57 %
5G network related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	25 %	0 %	0 %
Network handover related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %
Subtotal: Network related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	75 %	75 %	14 %	50 %	60 %
Total	93 %	95 %	94 %	58 %	76 %	94 %	81 %	96 %	83 %	80 %	48 %	28 %	59 %

After the first set of lab trials, the main work on the use cases focused on their integration with the related CAM services in the CAM Services Platform. This integration is performed in 2023 and will be reported in D3.9. This report contains in Annex 1 the description of the integration and testing for a single use case (UC1.3 low-latency video transmission). The CAM Services Platform has been deployed and initially tested in an experimental environment at CTTC laboratory in Barcelona. The use case under test includes the “video proxy” CAM service. This CAM service is virtualised in the CAM service platform and is deployed at the start of an experiment. The CAM service follows the UE, and when the UE is about to cross the border and switch domains, the CAM service is instantiated in the second domain. The UE communicates with the enablers from the CAM service platform to allow a smooth transition between the different instances of the CAM service.

1 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across 3 EU member states' borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways and shipways throughout Europe [1].

The scope of this deliverable is to report on the integration tests and the field trial readiness verification performed by the different use cases for the 5G NSA trials, which were planned to be performed in the second half of 2022.

1.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D3.8</i>	<i>D3.8 Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v1.0</i>	<i>This document</i>	
TASKS			
<i>T3.4 Lab trials and operational readiness for large scale field trials</i>	<i>The aim of this task is to conduct preliminary tests to assess the performance of the network and the CAM ecosystem and technically validate the proper operation of the use cases in lab environments, including the connectivity of the on-board units, network infrastructure, the behaviour of autonomous vehicles, to reduce the ambiguities prior to large-scale field trial validation.</i>	<i>Chapter 3</i>	<i>This report describes the local integration tests performed at the use case leader's sites.</i>

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<i>Lab trials will be conducted over three 5G testbeds, i.e. CTTC in Barcelona, TTU in Tallinn and VTT in Tampere.</i>		<i>The CTTC and TTU lab sites will be extensively used for testing the use cases with the enablers developed in WP2. This will be mainly done in the 2nd and 3rd set of lab trials.</i>
	<i>These initial trials will benchmark against target network and service-level KPIs the eMBB, URLLC and mMTC service class requirements and features of the V2X devices before deploying them to larger scale 5G corridor infrastructure. As far as the automotive use cases are concerned, the parameters of the OBUs and RSUs will be optimised to meet the connected and automated driving function requirements.</i>	Chapter 3	<i>Tests during the first set of lab trials have been concentrated on testing the functionality of the use case. In case 5G test networks are available near the developer's facilities, these have been used to test the use case.</i>

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

1.2.1 Relation to Other Deliverables

This deliverable takes input from the following deliverables:

- D1.1 [1] and D1.9 [2]: description of the use cases and the KPIs.
- D1.3 [3] and D3.1 [4]: description of the 5G networks.
- D1.7 [5] and D1.12 [6]: description of the test assessment framework.
- D2.1 [7], D2.3 [8], D2.5 [9] and D2.9 [11]: description of the 5G-ROUTES framework and the enablers.
- D2.7 [10]: description of the Tenant Web Portal functionalities.
- D3.3 [12]: description of the CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime.

1.2.2 Deliverable Structure

The main purpose of this deliverable is to report on the integration work of the use cases, the lab trials and the field trial readiness verification.

Chapter 2 describes the methodology used for the lab trials and the field trial readiness verification.

Chapter 3 describes the work performed for the various use cases: the architecture and sequence diagram of the use cases, the integration work, the lab trials and the field trial readiness verification results. Field trial readiness verification is based on checklists.

Chapter 4 provides conclusions and recommendations.

Annex 1 contains the detailed checklists for verification of 5G NSA field trial readiness.

Annex 2 contains, for a single use case, a description of the interaction between the user equipment, and the CAM services and enablers from the CAM Services Platform, as well as the testing of the integration. This work has been performed in 2023. The integration of the use cases with the CAM Services Platform will be reported in D3.9.

2 Methodology

2.1 Role of Lab Trials in the Project

2.1.1 5G-ROUTES Iterative Approach

- One of the key objectives of the 5G-ROUTES project is to provide a practical and novel 5G Platform specialised in the field of CAM services with emphasis on cross-domain scenarios. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is a multi-cloud system (core and edge) built as the combination of innovative technological enablers developed within the project to comply with the needs of CAM use cases [7]. Enablers are to be understood in this project as pieces of software that facilitate an enhancement or new functionality over a 5G Infrastructure. Each enabler offers and/or produces functionalities from the 5G-ROUTES Platform to the use case services. The enablers of the 5G-ROUTES platform will be implemented first for testing in selected lab environments (CTTC), and consecutively in the field trial environment in Latvia and Estonia. The time plan for the various enablers is detailed in D2.9 [11].

The technical KPIs of each use case will be evaluated during the field trials, to illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application performance. 5G-ROUTES use cases will showcase a wide gamut of CAM services, each with a unique set of network-related and application-related KPIs. The impact of 5G technologies and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers on the aforementioned KPIs will be measured and quantified. A special emphasis will be placed on service continuity, i.e., how the application performance is impacted during handovers between 5G telecom operators or between cellular and satellite connectivity. Multiple cross-border scenarios will be tested in field trials, involving multimodal modes of transport (i.e., automotive and maritime). Conclusions and recommendations will be drawn including recommendations for further field trials. When possible, the impact of 5G deployment will be also analysed so to potentially allow MNOs to evaluate their 5G network deployment scope, pattern and duration.

There are two types of tests in 5G-ROUTES:

- **Technical testing in lab trials.** The purpose of the lab trials is to test the functionalities and the readiness of the use cases in restricted closed areas and allow the fine-tuning of the 5G technological enablers which will be integrated in the large-scale field trials, to address most of the challenges, minimise the risks and reduce the uncertainties before the large-scale field trials are set and executed. For assuring readiness of the use cases to proceed to the field trials, the verification approach from the 5G-MOBIX project [15] will be used.

There are two types of lab trials:

- trials performed locally near the use case developers' facilities, to test use case functionality, potentially with tests in local 5G test networks, 5G commercial networks or in closed test tracks.
 - trials in test labs, especially CTTC and TTU, with the purpose of testing the integration of the use cases with the CAM Services Platform, developed in 5G-ROUTES.
- **Field trials** validate the capabilities of both the 5G technology and the use cases of the vertical industries (i.e., automotive, infotainment, transport/logistics) to enable their commercial exploitation. During the project, each use case will deploy a layered testing practice to drive development, involving significant industry representative tests, verifications, and validations.

This document describes the lab test trials in preparation of the planned 5G NSA field trials, which were planned to take place in Autumn 2022. Due to the requirement to refocus the trials and due to the delay of 5G roaming availability, the original trial plan was modified. The original first set of trials with 5G NSA, was discarded in order to reserve sufficient resources for 5G SA tests.

The decision to cancel the 5G NSA field trials was made in August 2022, when the trials, reported in this document, were finished. In Autumn 2022, also the use cases were restructured, and the following changes were made in the use cases:

- UC3.2 was cancelled due to limited cross-border aspects;
- UC5.3 was cancelled as the planned rail network is not deployed;
- UC2.2 was cancelled as the cross-border aspects are handled in other use cases;
- UC3.3 focus was changed from Vulnerable Road Users to roadworks;
- UC5.2 focus was changed to video transmission in maritime environment;
- UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3 are combined in a single use case “See-through platooning”, keeping the main features from the original use cases;
- UC2.1, UC3.1 and UC3.3 are combined in a single use case “Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving”, keeping main features of the original use cases.

2.1.2 General Test Process

The process for technical performance testing of the use cases consists of the follow phases:

- The use case KPIs are defined in D1.9, and the way they are measured in the field trials in D1.12. The test scenarios will be described in D4.1.
- During the lab trial phase, the functionality of the use case components is verified. The verification is performed by the use case leaders in their own facilities or in test facilities to which they have access.
- At the end of the first lab trial phase, the readiness for the 5G NSA field trials is verified. The purpose of the lab trials is to verify that the use case works as expected, and that all components are in place for the field trials. The field trial readiness verification is explained in more detail in section 2.3.
- During use case development, each use case integrates logging of the data. The data is stored in the Tenant Web Portal database, which also provides functionalities for synchronisation of the logging of the data, and for data upload and download. KPIs are calculated from the collected data and the calculated KPIs are transferred back to the Tenant Web Portal.
- The 5G NSA field trial cycle was planned to be performed in Autumn 2023.
- A second lab trial phase takes place during 2023. During these lab trials, focus is on the integration of the use cases with CAM services and with the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform, consisting of the enablers, which has been developed in WP2, as well as on cross-border issues. The use cases are tested together with the enablers, developed in WP2, in the labs. The second lab trials phase is reported in D3.9, which is planned for April 2024. This report includes in Annex 2 a description of the integration of a single use case, and the testing of the use case with the CAM Services Platform, performed in CTTC.
- The actual field trials consist of two phases. In the initial phase, planned for Spring 2024, a few simple scenarios are executed, and measurement performed focusing on the cross-border behaviour, and on validating the interaction between the use cases and the CAM Services Platform. The second phase, planned for Summer 2024, is concentrated on evaluating the final version of the use case implementations. The scenarios to be tested in the field trials are reported in D4.1. During the trial experiments are performed and data for the technical performance evaluation are collected. Based on the collected data, the use case specific technical PIs are calculated, and the evaluation results are reported in D4.6. The trial executions are reported in D4.5.

2.2 Availability of 5G-ROUTES Enablers for Lab Trials

The enablers which are developed in WP2, are integrated in the CAM Services Platform and deployed in a lab environment at CTTC. A more detailed description of the enablers, which are included in the CAM Services Platform and their timetable is provided in D2.9 [11].

During the first lab trials which are described in this report, only the enablers essential for the operation of the use cases in the NSA field trials, are tested, i.e., the V2X message routing service and the Tenant Web Portal. For the 5G NSA field trials these enablers are installed at public networks, whereas in the 5G SA field trials they will be deployed in the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform.

2.2.1 Tenant Web Portal

The Tenant Web Portal (TWP), as described in D2.7, acts as a central hub for the collection of data produced during the 5G-ROUTES use case lab and field trials and serves as the main user interface of the project providing the functionality to the UC owners to initiate an experiment and to visualise the KPI results.

The Tenant Web Portal provides the following functionalities:

- Use case and Performance Indicator (PI) configuration: via the Tenant Web Portal, the use case leaders configure the PIs and thresholds for each of the use cases. The Composite Indicators are calculated using PI thresholds, as described in D1.9.
- Logging Control functionality: The Tenant Web Portal includes logging control functionalities for starting and stopping of logging, e.g., through transmission of a specific signal to all devices collecting information, including test identifier.
- Data collection: As per D1.12, data for the agnostic network measurements is collected using specific tools by each network operator. Data can be collected in two ways:
 - real-time data collection at the Tenant Web Portal, through an MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) functionality of the Integration Fabric. The Tenant Web Portal contains a MQTT client through which data can be collected. The components, which must collect the data, need to transmit the data according to a specified MQTT topic structure.
 - localised data collection, e.g., at the vehicles involved in the field trials. After each specific test repetition or test run, data is uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal e.g., using MQTT or manual upload.
- Data Processing and KPI visualisation: KPIs are calculated from the collected data and visualised.
- Data storage: The Tenant Web Portal contains a database with both general information on the tests performed, the raw test data collected and the PIs. As an alternative to the actual raw data, the data can be stored by the test leader and transferred to a common accessible repository after quality assurance.
- Data download functionality: Use case leaders can download the data collected for quality assurance and analysis.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the interaction of the end user with the Tenant Web Portal during data collection and visualisation process.

Figure 1: Data collection process and KPI assessment using the Tenant Web Portal.

The Tenant Web Portal is hosted by eBOS. Access to a first version of the Tenant Web Portal was provided to all use case leaders in April 2022. During the lab trials the Tenant Web Portal was tested on the matter of usability, user interface, the integration with the UCs and data presentation. The Tenant Web Portal was also used for benchmarking the KPI calculation and visualisation process, as described in section 2.3.2. The version tested is implemented on the cloud, and allows to assign test IDs, configure the KPIs, enter KPI values, upload data files, and visualise the composite KPIs.

2.2.2 V2X Message Routing Service

The purpose of the V2X message routing enabler is to maintain a persistent connection in cross-border scenarios, while enabling V2X message sharing between road users connected to different networks. The V2X Message Routing Via MEC enabler allows vehicles to exchange the messages with low latency. Figure 2 shows the architecture of the V2X Message routing service. In this figure, vehicles in different domains are connected to the V2X broker, which is deployed on a local MEC. The V2X brokers in the different domains exchange messages with each other. The following protocols are identified at this point:

- V2MEC: Vehicle to MEC.
- MEC2MEC for communication between instances in different domains, or between an instance on the edge and in the cloud.

Figure 2: V2X Message Routing enabler Architecture

The communications between the broker and the users (V2MEC) are based on the MQTT communication protocol. The communication between MEC's and the broker and the back office are based on the AMQP (Advanced Message Queuing Protocol) communication protocol, aiming to be compliant with the IP-based protocol from the C-ROADS platform [17]. The messages from the broker are routed to the interested parties based on the quadtree tile information, which is a method to build a data structure for distributing data streams with respect to geographic areas (single points, lines or links, areas), and is often used in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and backend servers [18].

For the first set of lab trials and the 5G NSA field trials, the V2X Message Routing service is hosted and operated by VTT in Oulu, Finland. The first version provided to the partners is only a single instance, and hence only the MQTT broker is used, and not the AMQP based connection between two instances of the V2X Message Routing service. Access to the service is provided to 5G-ROUTES partners on request.

2.3 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The method to assure that the use cases are ready to proceed to the field trials is based on the verification approach from the 5G-MOBIX project [15].

2.3.1 Sequence Diagram

The sequence diagrams serve as the main tool for the verification and define the data flow for each of the use case scenarios which will be trialled. For field trial readiness verification, we concentrate on the data communication between components or infrastructure, which are provided by different partners. For the different checkpoints, the verification tests must be defined in more detail.

The different checkpoints in the sequence diagram are identified. The checkpoints correspond to either interactions between different components or to outputs of specific components, e.g., algorithms for collision detection. The verification will mainly concentrate on the checkpoints involving different actors.

The sequence diagrams shown in this report for the use cases are at application level and show the interactions between the User Equipment (UE) and the application services and enablers used in the use cases. The sequence diagrams are developed for the 5G NSA tests, in which the CAM Services Platform is not deployed yet. During these trials, the CAM services and enablers, which will be part of the CAM Services Platform, are deployed at the cloud. Hence, when the UE crosses the border, and when connection to the second network is established, the UEs will connect to the same enablers and CAM services as in the first network. The lower-level interactions between the UEs and the networks, which may depend upon the UE chipset or the network configuration, are not addressed in these sequence diagrams.

Figure 3 gives the example of the sequence diagram for the use case 3.1 (Sensor info sharing). In this example, an object is detected by a connected vehicle (CV1). The vehicle builds a CPM (Cooperative Perception Message), which is published. The V2X broker, to which the vehicle is connected, routes the message to actors, who have subscribed to the messages in the area. To ensure interoperability of the CPM with the messages generated by the other use cases generating CPMs (UC2.1 and UC3.3) these use cases are included in the sequence diagram. The connected vehicle CV2 receives the message, fuses the data with other observations, and warns the driver if needed.

Figure 3: Sequence Diagram for use case 3.1 (Sensor info sharing)

For each of the multi-actor checkpoints the required tests are identified. The test definition includes the test case objective, the components and the partners to be involved, as well as where the test will be performed. In order

to optimally use the resources, e.g., in order to avoid travel and transport of vehicles over long distances, it should be assessed whether and how tests can be performed remotely. Test cases must be defined for the checkpoints, both for the transmission of the message, but also for setting up and activating the connection between the different components involved in checkpoints.

Table 3: Checkpoint test definitions for UC3.1

Check-point	Multi-actor?	Test objective	Component(s)	From	To	Verification location
1	N	extraction of object metadata and CPM generation	CV1 sensor processing, OBU app	VTT	VTT	VTT
2	N	publishing of CPM to V2X broker	CV1 OBU app, V2X broker	VTT	VTT	VTT
3	Y	publishing of CPM by other actors	V2X broker	SWM, VED	VTT	VTT
4	N	geo-messaging of the broker	V2X broker	VTT	VTT	VTT
5	Y	receipt of CPM by vehicle - assuring message interoperability	V2X broker, CV OBU app	VTT, SWM, VED	VTT, SWM, VED	to be verified between SWM, VED and VTT
6	N	fusion of data (CPM and own observations)	CV OBU app	VTT	VTT	VTT
7	N	warn driver	CV OBU app	VTT	VTT	VTT

Remote verification should be used as much as possible, for optimal use of the resources. This can be realised e.g., through remote connection to servers, exchange of files containing the messages to be transmitted, etc. Connectivity of modem equipment is planned to be tested by involving local partners and use of the same modem equipment.

2.3.2 KPI Benchmarking

In D1.9 the KPIs for the different use cases are identified, as well as a processes defined for calculating composite KPIs. The KPIs, identified in D1.9 are integrated in the first version of the Tenant Web Portal. The benchmarking process consists of:

- performing measurements for a specific test scenario of a use case;
- assessing the quality of the measurements, e.g., assuring whether all measurements are synchronised with each other, and that all data needed for the calculation of the KPIs have been logged;
- calculating the indicators of metrics, like median or 95% percentile of end-to-end latency, for the test scenario;
- entering the data of the calculated metrics in the Tenant Web Portal;
- assessing the values of extended indicators, which cannot be directly measured;
- assessing the target values of the smart performance indicators;
- visualisation of the KPIs in the Tenant Web Portal.

Based on the results of this exercise, the approach developed in D1.9 and D1.12 is validated and, if needed, updated prior to the calculation of the KPIs for the first set of field trials.

The use case leaders have tested the Tenant Web Portal and have proposed changes to the Tenant Web Portal. Figure 4 provides a screenshot of the representation of test results pin the Tenant Web Portal for the measurements of UC3.1, shown in Figure 41.

Figure 4: Visualisation of measurement results in Tenant Web Portal

During the lab trial tests some issues with the KPI methodology were identified:

- the need for functionalities to perform statistical analysis of the experiments of a single scenario, and the visualisation of the aggregated values;
- the results and the visualisation of the results depends highly on the threshold values set by the use case leader. The threshold values, especially the value for “bad” are often hard to assess.

2.3.3 Verification Checklist

For assuring that the use case is ready for proceeding to the field trials, a verification checklist, based on the checklist developed in the 5G-MOBIX project [15], is used. The checklist is based on self-assessment by the developing partners.

There will be different versions of the checklist for the different field trial phases, each one corresponding to a specific “Release” of the use case and the trial phase to be performed. There will be specific tests for each of the enablers. Additionally, there is a column for the location, to indicate where the test is performed (e.g., at the use case developer premises, at a lab e.g., CTTC, through remote connections). The checklist addresses issues, which can be grouped in the following groups:

- **Use case specific tests:**
 - **vehicle related issues:** issues related to the vehicle and the sensors and applications installed in the vehicles;
 - **OBU (On-Board Unit) related issues:** issues related to the OBU, which is installed in the vehicles. For the field trials, the Mikrotik 5G [24] is used, and a limited set is also made available by LMT for testing. For the lab trials, use cases may also use other modems which have been proven to work in the 5G test or commercial networks in which the lab trials are performed;

- **infrastructure related issues:** for those use cases, which rely on road-side equipment, issues related to sensors and other road-side infrastructure which communicates with the network;
- **external servers:** issues related to backend servers, which are used by the use cases;
- **other end-user devices related issues:** for those use cases, which use end-user devices, such as smart phones;
- **CAM services related issues:** CAM services are pieces of software which are mainly used by a single use case, which will be deployed as VNFs (Virtual Network Functions) in the CAM Services Platform. A list of the CAM services is included in D3.3 [12]. The CAM services are in 5G NSA field trials installed on the cloud, under the responsibility of the use case. Only in the 5G SA field trials they will be part of the CAM Services Platform;
- **privacy and security related issues:** this involves both GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) related issues, as well as protocols and processes for data security.
- **Enabler related tests:** tests related to the integration of the use cases with the enablers. For the first set of field trials, this involves:
 - V2X broker, described in section 2.2.2.
 - Tenant Web Portal, described in section 2.2.1.
- **Network related tests:** test related to the integration of the use cases with the field trial networks. These tests are performed by the local MNOs and local partners, using the modems which will be used in the field trials.

The specific tests are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Issues addressed in the verification checklist

Vehicle related issues	
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control
V9	Permits: all necessary permits for performing the tests, including driving on public roads, have been received
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
OBU related issues	
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated
V14	The OBUs can manage and run 3 rd party the required applications
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network
V16	The OBUs have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU

V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
Infrastructure related issues	
I1	The availability of the infrastructure sensors is assured
I2	The infrastructure sensors connect and have access to the 5G network
I3	The infrastructure sensors have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform
I4	The infrastructure sensors are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding
I5	Synchronisation measures are used for the infrastructure
I6	Applications at the infrastructure (edge) are working correctly and have real-time access to all required data
I7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network
I8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
External servers	
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRU devices, smartphones)	
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network
D3	The end-user devices have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected
D5	The end-user devices are capable to transmit the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
CAM-services related issues	
C1	The CAM-services can be deployed in the field trial site
C2	The CAM-services can connect to all relevant end-user devices, 5G-ROUTES enablers and external servers
C3	The CAM services have access to all required data
C4	The CAM services behave as expected and have been validated
C5	The CAM services are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding
C6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests
Enabler related issues	
Specific checks will be included for all enablers which are used by the use cases.	
Tenant Web Portal	
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal
ET3	Data logging can be stopped, and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal

ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other
V2X broker	
EV1	The end-user applications can connect to the V2X broker
EV2	The end-user applications publish messages according to the agreed protocol
EV3	The end-user applications receive the messages to which they have subscribed
EV4	The algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages work as expected
EV5	Metrics (can be logged) and can be downloaded
5G network related issues	
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised
Network handover related issues	
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2
N8	All relevant information is exchanged when moving between networks
Privacy and security issues	
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...
P2	All partners have agreed on the processes for exchanging certificates and have access to the agreed certificates.
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)

The checklist is filled in as an Excel document. The responsible partner performs a self-assessment of the test on whether it fulfils the requirements. The test result is either “Passed”, “Fail”, “Partially passed”, “not tested” or “not relevant”. The completion percentage for each of the areas and for the complete checklist is calculated as:

Completion percentage = $(\#Passed + \#Partially/2)/(\#Passed + \#Partially + \#Failed + \#Not_Tested)$.

The Excel file contains 3 checklists, one for each release (or field trials). The checklists for the later trials inherit the results of the checklist for the first release. The checklists, which have been filled in by the use case leaders, are included in Annex 1 to this document. An overview of the results, following the grouping of the issues mentioned above, is included in the description of the use case tests in the following chapter.

2.3.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification Process

As indicated in the previous section, the verification checklist contains checks for both the performance of the use case, as well as the integration of the use case with the enablers and the integration of the use case in the network.

For the first field trial runs, which are performed in the 5G NSA networks of LMT and Telia at the virtual cross-border site in Bikernieki, the only enablers which are in use are the V2X Message Routing service and the Tenant Web Portal. Access to the V2X Message Routing enabler was provided in February 2022. Access to a draft version of the Tenant Web Portal with limited functionalities was provided in April 2022.

2.3.4.1 Network tests

For the field trials, the Mikrotik 5G router [24] will be used by almost all use cases, except when specific devices such as smartphones are used. The use of a single modem for all use cases simplifies the testing process: if tests performed with the modems in the field trial sites by the local partners are successful, the use case participants

can assume that the modem will also work for their use cases in the field trial site. The Mikrotik 5G router has been developed in close collaboration of Mikrotik and LMT. Detailed tests of the router have been performed in Mikrotik 5G lab environment in Riga which is provided by LMT. Some of the measurements as traffic monitoring, signal strength and SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio) are shown in Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7, Figure 8 shows an overall view of interfaces monitoring view. In April 2022 basic tests have been performed by Telia as well. Coverage tests have been performed in Bikernieki, where the whole racetrack is covered.

Figure 5: Traffic monitoring tests

Figure 6: Signal monitoring tests

Figure 7: SNR tests

Figure 8: Interfaces status view

2.3.4.2 Roaming tests

Roaming and handover tests were performed in Bikernieki and demonstrated in May 2022 during a demo for the 5G-ROUTES reviewers. The results of the tests for use cases UC3.2 and UC3.3, which were demonstrated, are described in more detail in sections 3.7.4 and 3.8.4.

3 Use Case Overview

This section gives an overview of the lab trials and the checks for field trial readiness per use case. For each use case, first a brief introduction is provided, including the scenarios, the use case roadmap, the components and the sequence diagram. The roadmap indicates which use case and network functionalities will be tested in the different lab trials and field trials. The introduction is followed by a description of how lab trials and the verification for field trial readiness were performed, followed by the results of lab trials and the verification. The next steps are then described: what is still needed prior to go to the field trials.

3.1 UC1.1 Dynamic Vehicles Platooning

3.1.1 Use Case Overview

The goal of UC1.1 is to form a string of vehicles travelling as close as safely possible to each other, making use of URLLC, thus enabling shorter inter-vehicle distances than with purely sensor-based perception (Figure 9).

Figure 9: UC1.1 visualisation.

3.1.1.1 Use Case Description

Vehicles driving in a high-speed platoon require sensors for measuring the distance of the preceding vehicle, and fast and reliable network communication for exchanging kinematics data (speed and acceleration) with participating vehicles. To test the performance of sensors and network interfaces, the following scenarios are planned to be executed in the first trial phase, using two vehicles:

1. **Telemetry exchange without driving:** let both vehicles exchange telemetry data while stationary
2. **Vehicle following (with and without communication):** let the automated vehicle follow a manually controlled vehicle, once with radar-only sensing, and once with communication enabled.
3. **Simulated cross-border test:** let the automated vehicle follow a manually controlled vehicle and simulate a network interruption.

The KPIs that will be mainly focused on in the first trial phase are network KPIs, including bandwidth, reliability and latency, as these are critical for all use cases led by EDI (UC1.1 and UC1.2). The secondary set of KPI measurements for this use case involves longitudinal and lateral distance deviations between vehicles.

3.1.1.2 Roadmap of UC1.1 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

The long-term trial plan for UC1.1 involves a gradual increase in complexity of the platooning system. This will be done by increasing the number of vehicles and exploring the extent to which inter-vehicle distances can be decreased while increasing platoon speeds. Another aspect that will be tested in the upcoming trial phases, is the performance difference between 5G NSA and 5G SA implementations of vehicle platoon. Thus, the goal of the first trials is to verify the fundamental functionality of the platooning system, and the following trials are planned to build upon these results.

- **Lab trial #1:** low-latency kinematics data exchange between two vehicles in 5G NSA networks
- **Field trial #1:** low-latency kinematics data exchange between two vehicles in a cross-border situation
- **Lab trial #2:** platooning between two vehicles in 5G NSA networks
- **Field trial #2:** platooning between two vehicles in 5G NSA networks in a cross-border situation
- **Lab trial #3:** platooning between two or more vehicles in 5G SA networks and dynamic manoeuvring
- **Field trial #3:** platooning between two or more vehicles in 5G SA networks and dynamic manoeuvring in a cross-border situation

3.1.1.3 Components

The following components are relevant for a complete execution and evaluation of UC1.1:

- Connected autonomous vehicle (CAV) on-board unit (OBU):
 - DbW system (vehicle actuation)
 - Radar and camera (longitudinal distance estimation)
 - 5G modem (kinematics data exchange)
 - Automotive grade computation platform (main computing unit)
 - Power equipment (for powering computer and peripherals)
 - LIDAR (localisation in HD map)
- Software (EDI CCAM platform):
 - vehicle control system and platoon manager
 - MQTT client
- MQTT broker (server and software)

To verify target KPIs, we make use of the Wireshark software to extract all relevant network and vehicle data from any given trial run.

3.1.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Apart from the leading vehicle, all vehicles participating in a platoon must perform the following operations:

1. Transmit own kinematic data via MQTT
2. Receive kinematic data from other vehicles and apply control

Figure 10 shows the process of transmitting kinematics data of participating vehicles to the V2X broker, including network interruption and reconnection mechanisms.

Figure 10: UC1.1 vehicle data publisher sequence diagram.

The leading vehicle is mainly concerned with publishing sensor data, since it is generally controlled by a human driver (or a lane-following routine), while the following vehicle does both: publish its own kinematics and subscribe to leading vehicle data.

The platoon-start request is initiated by the leading vehicle via the Platoon Management Service, which then provides the vehicle with necessary information for communicating with the V2X broker, upon which the vehicle’s OBU can start to transmit platooning-relevant information to the broker. The Platoon Management Service is used for keeping track of the identity and order of vehicles. It is located in the cloud, as it has less stringent timing requirements than the V2X broker, which is used for low-latency sensor data sharing. A following

vehicle may then join the platoon through a similar process, which must be accepted by the leading vehicle. Then it can launch its Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (CACC) system to become part of the platoon.

A network interruption automatically triggers the offline backup controller of following vehicles through a system that monitors the rate of incoming messages. This forces all platoon participants to increase inter-vehicle distances for safety. At the same time, the OBUs continuously attempt to reach the V2X broker. Once reconnected, the vehicles automatically restart publishing sensor data, thus re-enabling the platoon.

3.1.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

Basic functionality tests (DbW, radar, MQTT data exchange performance etc.) were performed at the EDI labs statically (between local PCs) and by driving within the EDI territory at low speeds. Most of these tests were performed from February to April 2022. Additional tests were done during 2023 and were mainly related to time synchronisation issues. More involved preparations for the field trials (starting in April 2023 and ongoing) take place on the Biķernieki racetrack (Figure 11), which is equipped with a network tower, on which both LMT and Telia cells are installed for a simulated cross-border environment. More details on these tests are given in the following section.

Figure 11: Biķernieki racetrack in Riga. 5G tower marked in orange.

EDI's use-case verification strategy involves performing separate tests for different hardware and software components (DbW system, MQTT communication, vehicle control algorithms etc.) before moving on to more complex tests that combine several functionalities at once (e.g. DbW actuation from control signals that have been obtained via MQTT). This ultimately leads to final verification tests that are as close to the field trials of as possible.

3.1.3 Lab Trial Results

All EDI lab trials were performed in the EDI lab or within EDI premises, where slow speed driving is possible. In order to obtain information about transmitted data from the vehicles, we use Wireshark. Data files obtained from this software can be parsed for further analysis, both for network KPIs and vehicle KPIs. The tests that have been performed within the 5G-ROUTES project in preparation of the 5G NSA field trials are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: List of already performed tests for UC1.1.

Test specification	Description
DbW system: test basic automated actuation functions.	Send manual commands (acceleration and brake pedal positions, steering torque) and evaluate behaviour.

<p>MQTT subscriber/publisher: test communication performance via MQTT broker.</p>	<p>Send and receive vehicle data via MQTT broker, measure loopback latency using EDI’s own server (results shown in Figure 12). A similar test was later repeated at the Bikernieki racetrack, in order to have conditions that are more similar to the final trials.</p>
<p>Control algorithms: validate the control algorithms that are later used for realising the use-case.</p>	<p>Produce a virtual feedback loop and evaluate the controller’s performance by using:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purely virtual input data and models 2. Data obtained from past recordings <p>The latter is visualised in Figure 14, which shows both the steering PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) and the Model Predictive Controller (MPC) for vehicle speed control. The plot shows the responsiveness of the respective controllers to a reference signal obtained from recorded vehicle data (speed and steering angle).</p>
<p>Live synchronized driving: initial integration test that combines multiple relevant functionalities.</p>	<p>Let a manually controlled vehicle send speed and steering angle information to the automated vehicle in real-time, which then executes the same driving behaviour. Example results of this test are shown in Figure 15.</p>
<p>Time synchronization: ensure minimal time offsets between participating vehicles.</p>	<p>Perform vehicle on-board-computer time synchronization with GPS and pulse-per-second (PPS) signals using the Chrony software, while driving on Biķernieki racetrack. The system-time offset of the on-board computers with respect to the GPS reference is shown in Figure 16.</p>

Figure 12: MQTT broker loopback test at EDI facilities

Figure 13: MQTT broker loopback test at Bikernieki racetrack

The loopback tests performed at EDI premises showed overall lower latencies due to shorter distances to the broker. On the racetrack we found no explicit correlation between vehicle speed and network performance, but the latency was affected by outside factors, like the vehicle’s position relative to the network tower and physical obstructions.

Figure 14: Control system performance using a virtual ego model and recorded data as inputs.

Figure 15: Control system performance in a synchronized driving test.

Both sets of control system tests showed adequate performance for moving on to more complex trials on the Bikernieki racetrack.

Figure 16: GPS time offset from vehicle on board computer.

In order to measure the latency KPI, all vehicles need to have a synchronized system time. The system time is synchronized using GPS receivers and its PPS output, which is connected to on-board computers' serial port. This test shows adequate synchronization offset.

3.1.4 Field Trial Readiness

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.1):

Table 6: Field trial readiness for UC1.1

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	8	0	1	0	94%
OBU related issues	10	0	0	0	100 %
External servers	5	0	1	0	92 %
UE related issues	23	0	2	0	96 %
Tenant Web Portal	5	0	3	0	81 %
Enabler related issues	5	0	3	0	81 %
5G network related issues	1	0	0	0	100 %
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100 %
Network related issues	4	0	0	0	100 %
Total	32	0	5	0	93 %

The performed tests so far have provided the following results:

- **Vehicle related issues:** trial readiness of the DbW system has been shown through tests with manual torque signals and integration of the DbW system in the control loop with virtual and recorded reference data, done in the EDI labs. The radar has been tested separately (more on this in section 3.5).
- **OBU related issues and external servers:** the vehicles have been successfully tested with the Mikrotik routers, which are planned to be used during the final trials.
- **Tenant Web Portal:** test definition and data entry capabilities have been tested. Complete integration tests of portal in the test cycles are still to be done.
- **5G network:** the availability of 5G NSA was tested in a synchronized driving test on the Bikernieki racetrack, using a Mikrotik router. Higher-level issues have been tested by MNOs.
- **Privacy and security:** for this use-case, there are no privacy-related issues, as only vehicle kinematics data is being exchanged between vehicles.

3.1.5 Next Steps

Prior to the field trials, the management service for the management of the platoon which keeps track of the status of the vehicles in the platoon, will be finalized.

The logging capabilities of the system will be finalized, and the vehicle functions will be adapted depending on the detailed planning of the field trials.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC1.2 and UC1.3 in a single use case “See-through platooning”. The use case will be integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform to assure service continuity when crossing borders.

3.2 UC1.2 Cooperative Lane Change

3.2.1 Use Case Overview

The goal of UC1.2 is to perform a lane change manoeuvre while coordinating movements with other vehicles, thus minimising any effects on traffic flow (Figure 17).

Figure 17: UC1.2 visualisation.

3.2.1.1 Use Case Description

Refer to section 3.1.1 (UC1.1) for relevant KPI information, as both use cases share similar metrics. The first field trial will be used to test aspects that are common to all EDI use cases (UC1.1 and UC1.2). In addition to common aspects, the following scenarios are planned to be tested for UC1.2:

1. **GPS-RTK (Real-Time Kinematics) and LIDAR-based localisation:** test transmission of lidar and GPS data between vehicles.
2. **Lane-keeping and lane change test:** test the vehicle's capability to stay in lane and perform a lane change manoeuvre, making use of the *Autoware* platform [12].

3.2.1.2 Roadmap of UC1.2 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

Similar to UC1.1, the long-term trial plan for UC1.2 is to gradually increase its complexity. The first trial will be used to test a single-car lane-change manoeuvre and localization performance. For further trials, there will be additional vehicles on the neighbouring lane to execute more involved cooperative manoeuvres, while also taking into account risks of network disruption during the manoeuvre. Different localization strategies will also be considered, with lidar-based positioning in HD-maps, including lane information, and GPS- and camera-based positioning with lane detection done optically.

3.2.1.3 Components

The following components are relevant for a complete execution and evaluation of UC1.2:

- Connected autonomous vehicle (CAV) on-board unit (OBU) by EDI:
 - DbW system (vehicle actuation)
 - Radar (lateral and longitudinal distance measurement)
 - 5G modem (kinematics data exchange)
 - Automotive grade computation platform (main computing unit)
 - Power equipment (for powering computer and peripherals)
 - LIDAR + GPS RTK (produce HD (High-Definition) maps and localise vehicle in them)
- Software (EDI CCAM platform):
 - vehicle control system (control algorithms reporting to DbW system)
 - MQTT client (transmission and reception inter-vehicle data)
 - CAN drivers and other interfaces
 - *Autoware* platform for additional manoeuvres based on HD maps
- MQTT broker (server and software)

Refer to section 5 in D3.3 for more information on components and architecture.

3.2.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Similar to UC1.1, vehicles participating in cooperative lane change fulfil at least one of two roles:

1. Transmit own kinematic data via MQTT;
2. Receive kinematic data from other vehicles and apply control.

Due to these similarities to UC1.1, the following sequence diagram focuses more on in-vehicle aspects that lead to a successful execution of a lane-change manoeuvre (Figure 18).

Figure 18: UC1.2 communication and control system sequence diagram.

3.2.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

Refer to Section 3.1.2 (UC1.1) for information about trial locations.

EDI’s use case verification strategy involves performing separate tests for different hardware and software components (DbW system, MQTT communication, vehicle control algorithms, etc.) before moving on to more complex tests that combine several functionalities at once (e.g. DbW actuation from control signals that have been obtained via MQTT). This ultimately leads to final verification tests that are as close to the field trials as possible.

3.2.3 Lab Trial Results

The following table describes additional tests performed for UC1.2 that are not covered by UC1.1 tests.

Table 7: List of already performed tests for UC1.2.

Test specification	Description
LIDAR localisation	Record LIDAR data in Valka/Valga and Biķernieki and perform offline NDT (Normal Distributions Transform) matching for vehicle localisation in an HD map (Figure 19).
GPS RTK localisation	Record GNSS data in the streets around EDI labs, evaluate signal strength and localisation accuracy.
Virtual map evaluation	Create an HD map of Biķernieki (Figure 20) and integrate it in the CARLA [20] simulator (while researching the optimal point cloud density for best performance and accuracy trade-offs).

Figure 19: Vehicle localisation in a LIDAR point cloud.

Figure 20: HD-map of a portion of the Biķernieki track.

3.2.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

Table 8 gives an overview of the status of the field trial readiness verification, based on the checklist, which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.2):

Table 8: Field trial readiness for UC1.2

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	9	0	0	0	100 %
OBU related issues	10	0	0	0	100 %
External servers	5	0	1	0	92 %
UE related issues	24	0	1	0	98 %
Tenant Web Portal	5	0	3	0	81 %
Enabler related issues	5	0	3	0	81 %
5G network related issues	1	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	4	0	0	0	100%
Total	33	0	4	0	95 %

For the context of the first trial phase, a large part of the results described in 3.1.4 are equally relevant for UC1.2. The following points can be noted about results specific for UC1.2:

- **Vehicle related issues:** while the functionality of GPS and lidar sensors has been validated, they are yet to be tested as part of a control loop.
- **Privacy and security:** for this use-case, there are no privacy-related issues, and any usage of optical sensors like cameras is only meant to yield relevant metadata like lane markings.

3.2.5 Next Steps

The next steps for UC1.2 involve integration tests that validate the lane-change routine in the context of a cooperative driving scenario.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC1.1 and UC1.3 in a single use case “See-through platooning”. The use case will be integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform to assure service continuity when crossing borders.

3.3 UC1.3 See-Through View for Safe Automated Overtake

3.3.1 Use Case Overview

The use case relies on the capability of 5G networks to offer broadband video services in mobile environments. In such a scenario, a car is stuck behind a slow vehicle and does not have a clear view to safely overtake. To do so, the car willing to overtake receives (through a manual request) a video stream from the slow one, permitting the driver to have a broader visual over the road and enabling a safe manoeuvre.

Figure 21: Real-time video transmission for automated overtaking scenario

3.3.1.1 Use Case Description

The scenario where the overtaking manoeuvring takes place is at the border of two countries, in order to have a network handover scenario during the ego vehicle's surpassing process. The main objective is to assess the performance of the video streaming system in a cross-border situation.

Data is collected in both cars: the measurement software Qosium [20] is utilised to measure the network KPIs during the uplink and downlink video transmissions. All the KPIs are collected in a single text file (one for every Qosium Scope instance running a measurement). Afterwards, the file is manually uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal.

The target KPIs to satisfy are:

- E2E latency, with 50 ms for both UL/DL (Upload/Download) communication and about 200 ms for the user-perceived latency.
- Throughput of 15 Mbps, which corresponds to a typical HD video.

3.3.1.2 Roadmap in the 5G-ROUTES Project

For UC1.3 two vehicles/OBUs are involved (one with camera, the second receiving data). The overtaking is planned to be performed with VTT's vehicle during the third field trial, when the roads are temporarily closed to other traffic participants – during the first and second field trial only the information exchange will be evaluated. For the E2E latency measurements only one car will be utilised.

- **Lab trial #1:** Low-latency video transmission between two UEs using MEC in 5G NSA networks. For easier verification, in the lab trials both UEs are installed in the same vehicle.
- **Field trial #1:** Low-latency video transmission between two vehicles in NSA networks in cross-border situations
- **Lab trial #2:** Low-latency video transmission between two vehicles using MEC in 5G SA networks.
- **Field trial #2:** Low-latency video transmission between two vehicles in 5G SA networks in cross-border situations
- **Lab trial #3:** low-latency video transmission and automated overtaking
- **Field trial #3:** low-latency video transmission and automated overtaking in 5G SA networks in cross-border situations

3.3.1.3 Components

To verify the target KPIs we proceeded to build in Oulu and Helsinki our first static indoor testbeds to assess our network and devices behaviours while sending low latency TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) video communication over our 5G VTT NSA test network. Afterwards we tested it in the Elisa public network in outdoor and indoor static situations.

Figure 22: Single MEC VTT Espoo testbed

The testbed, shown in Figure 22 utilises two Linux computers for streaming and collecting the measurements with Qosium. The front vehicle’s computer utilises as a video source the Logitech Brio 4K camera, connected to a USB port. The front vehicle uses a local script to transcode the video to a public RTMP/RTSP (Real-Time Messaging Protocol/ Real-Time Streaming Protocol) MEC server hosted at VTT. The client who requests to see the video requests it at the proxy server and displays it on its screen. Both computers are wired connected to a 5G terminal, which connects them to the 5G NSA/SA network.

3.3.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 23: Overtaking UC1.3 sequence diagram

Figure 23 shows the sequence diagram of the overtaking manoeuvre in a cross-border situation, when there are MECs at both networks. In addition, the figure represents, from the application point of view, the interaction of the video application with the MEC, when crossing a virtual border without the support of the 5G-ROUTES technical enablers.

When the UC1.3 scenario starts, the CAV1 vehicle reports the availability of its front camera view to the network cell it is currently located. More specifically, CAV1 sends the video stream to a local edge server. When the following automated vehicle wants to safely overtake, it requests to the network what the slow vehicle sees. In this video request, CAV2 vehicle can “see through” the car ahead, but the range of the on-board sensors are not sufficient to prove that overtaking is safe enough. It is therefore the responsibility of the driver to decide whether it is safe to overtake or not. Based on the transmitted video, the driver confirms that the automated overtaking manoeuvre can be initiated. Once the overtaking manoeuvre is performed, the video transmission stops.

During a border crossing, this kind of service is generally disrupted due to the handover procedures, introducing image freezing. Hence, to guarantee service continuity handover should be as fast as possible. Two 5G network functionalities are planned to be used, which are Slicing and Mobile Edge Computing. Slicing will allocate and separate two services: one dedicated to enhancing mobile broadband, so video transmission itself, and the other one to low latency V2X critical messaging. Slicing will only be tested during the 5G SA field trials. The Assisted handover enabler will be used to minimise the service disruption during network change, by informing both cars of the video service IP address at the other side of the border.

The MEC’s platform role, instead, is to ensure low-latency communication among the vehicles and to provide the slicing isolation. Moreover, the presence of a distributed MEC-enabled 5G network will be beneficial to host computational power for data/video processing.

In case there is no CAM Services Platform, as will be the case during the first set of 5G NSA field trials, the video proxy will be operated in the cloud. During the 5G SA field trials, the video proxy will be deployed in the CAM Services Platform.

In the laboratory tests the initiation and termination of network connections were deliberately controlled to simulate the cross-border impact. To recreate the network disconnection effect, the video proxy application running in MEC 1 has been stopped to force the CAV1 and CAV2 to respectively start pushing and requesting the video stream to the MEC2 IP address. The IP addresses of both MECs, located in Espoo and in Oulu were known a priori.

3.3.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The first lab trials were performed in VTT premises in Oulu and then mainly in the Espoo facilities in the end of 2021 and the beginning of 2022. Initially only the local 5GTN NSA test from VTT in the Espoo network has been utilised for static tests, but afterwards we proceed to use Elisa 5G SIM cards for the indoor and outdoor tests in commercial 5G NSA networks. Figure 24 shows the setup in VTT’s lab in Espoo, with two laptops connected to the 5G NSA 5GTN test network. The outdoor tests were performed in the Otaniemi area (Finland), close to the VTT facilities.

Figure 24: Setup in VTT's lab in Espoo: at left, the streaming laptop with camera and Netgear modem, at right the receiving laptop with Mikrotik modem

The lab verification process activities were mainly focused on checking the expected delays and packet losses from the video transmissions between different video servers in Espoo and Oulu. The main target was to assess whether the end-to-end user perceived latency KPI target of 200 ms can be achieved. Different video cameras have been tested in order to find the most suitable model to satisfy the delay requirements set for a smooth, low-latency and high-quality video stream.

3.3.3 Lab Trial Results

To measure the network communication delay we utilised the software Qosium, and for the E2E latency, we decided to take a screen clock capture technique, which basically consists of pointing the front-vehicle's video camera to the screen where the video is displayed (behind-vehicle computer screen). Taking the time difference of the time values displayed in the video screen loop, we obtain an approximated end-to-end latency. The DL and UL measurements have been taken respectively by measuring the delay between the camera and the MEC and from the latter to the user watching the video.

Looking at the test results of the February 2022 indoor tests in Espoo over the VTT's 5G NSA test network, we observed that the KPIs are satisfied, getting less than 15 ms for the communication (both for UL and DL) and under 180 ms for the E2E latency.

Similar results have been achieved for a first outdoor test, which had on average 200 ms for the E2E latency (over several manual time difference measurements) and values ranging from 15 to 25 ms for the UL and DL network communication, utilizing a 5 Mbps bitrate video transmission. During the first outdoor test we had a phone recording the location of the car, which permitted us to plot the delay's variability over the driving path.

Figure 25: UL and DL network delays obtained during our first outdoor trial in Otaniemi, Espoo

In a second outdoor trial taken in mid-April 2022, we had the chance to test the MikroTik 5G router (used for the uplink network interface), in order to compare how the delays and packet losses behave sending the video stream at first to the Espoo VTT public MEC server and then to the VTT Oulu MEC. As in the first trial, the video transmission configuration utilized a single video proxy MEC, which receives a video generated by a Logitech camera over RTSP TCP with a 15 Mbps average bitrate. In a preliminary indoor static test, we observed that the Oulu MEC has (on both UL and DL) 5 ms more network delay compared to the Espoo MEC.

During the test drive in Espoo, the network delay variation for both uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) remained stable, with values of 25ms and 10ms, respectively. However, in a particular road area experiencing shadowing, there was a temporary increase in delay by approximately 50 ms in both directions of measurement.

Figure 26: Uplink delay variation while driving over two shadowing areas

Repeating the same video streaming test over the Oulu’s MEC we observed a similar delay variation behaviour, with the UL and DL delays respectively at 30ms and 15ms, with an increase of about 50/60ms in the area poorly covered by the 5G Elisa NSA network. The video transmission quality has been constantly monitored during the driving test, which permitted to observe how the shadowing effect can temporarily generate video freezing effects and severe pixelization. Nonetheless, the video stream application running at the client side never stopped, and once back in the optimal area the video quality became normal.

We repeated the test at the end of May 2022 utilizing our VTT's 5GTN SA network (Open5gs core Rel. 16, RAN Rel. 15), utilizing the Netgear Nighthawk [25] and MikroTik [24] routers. Two 5G SA base stations serving the network connectivity are installed on top of the Futurehub building in Otaniemi, Espoo. Maintaining the same outdoor racing track, we proceeded to test our use case setup utilizing at first the Netgear as the car pushing the video and then the MikroTik, in order to see which router better performs in terms of delay. In the following pictures we can see that the Netgear has in a good coverage area about 15-25 ms and 900 ms in bad areas. We can observe in the traffic sent diagram that whenever the delay increases, the traffic decreases accordingly, and when the car comes back in the optimal coverage area it tries to catch up sending the video to the destination at a higher data rate.

Figure 27: Netgear's UL delay and traffic sent

Switching the Netgear with the MikroTik, we can see how more frequent poor performance, when the 5G SA coverage is lacking, raising the delay to 800ms several times. The minimum delay ranges between 20 ms to 26 ms. We observed in our indoor premises how the MikroTik struggles more than the Netgear to connect to the 5GTN network in NLOS (Non-Line-Of-Sight) areas.

Figure 28: MikroTik UL delay and traffic sent

In all the tests we utilized the VTT's NTP (Network Time Protocol) server in running in Mikes, Espoo, Finland. In the outdoor tests we utilized a U-Blox device [28] to collect the GNSS information and record/stored it with the software U-Center [29]. The GNSS location collection directly inside Qosium is under testing.

To summarize, the number of measurement files generated by the UC1.3 trial are mainly three:

1. Qosium-based text file for the UL network measurements (from the car pushing the video to the MEC)

2. Qosium file for the DL (MEC to the client displaying the video)
3. U-Center GNSS location file

A Qosium measurement file collects several KPIs e.g., traffic generated, network delay, jitter etc. between the primary and secondary probes.

3.3.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.3):

Table 9: Field trial readiness for UC1.3

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	9	0	0	0	100%
OBU related issues	7	0	0	0	100%
UE related issues	16	0	3	0	100%
CAM services	3	0	0	0	100%
Tenant Web Portal	5	0	0	2	71%
Enabler related issues	5	0	0	2	71%
5G network related issues	1	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	3	0	1	0	100%
Privacy and security issues	1	0	0	0	100%
Total	29	0	0	2	94 %

The issues which are still open are mainly related to the logging of the data, which has to be finalised.

- Vehicle related issues: the transmission of data has been tested in laptops, which can be installed in the vehicles. The tests on the performance of the video transmission have been described in the previous section.
- OBU related issues: the application has been tested with the Mikrotik 5G router, which will be used in the field trial tests
- CAM services: the video proxy CAM service has been tested on the MEC in VTT facilities and works as expected.
- Tenant Web Portal issues: the transfer of KPI data has been tested. The integration of the logging was implemented.
- Network related issues have been tested by the MNOs in Bikernieki.
- Privacy and security issues: a label is attached to the vehicle indicating streaming of video for research purposes.

3.3.5 Next Steps

The logging will be finalised, and then the use case will be later demonstrated in Bikernieki or Valga/Valka, depending on the detailed planning of the field trials.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC1.1 and UC1.2 in a single use case “See-through platooning”.

The use case is integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform to assure service continuity when crossing borders. The integration involves both the deployment of the “video proxy” CAM service in the CAM Services Platform. The use case makes also use of the V2X Message Routing service: CAM vehicle status messages are transmitted, which are used by the PRAE (Predictive Resource Allocation) in order to instantiate the video

proxy in the second network prior to crossing borders. The Assisted Service Continuity enabler is used to extract the IP address of the CAM service when crossing borders. The integration and the testing is described in Annex 2 of this report.

3.4 UC2.1 Real-Time Traffic Information and Cooperative Intersection Collision Control

3.4.1 Use Case Overview

3.4.1.1 Use Case Description

The primary goal of the use case is to assure and enable a reliable exchange of road traffic status data between autonomous “drivers” and road users through enhanced real-traffic video fed and controlled via V2X communication standards, making benefit of 5G network capabilities. The use case scenarios evaluate the service continuity and the C-ITS (Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems) services along the cross-border environment. The C-ITS services integrate the capabilities of AI with those of the 5G network to collect and interchange data improving road users’ safety.

Through the enhanced real-time traffic visual monitoring and the control of an intersection traffic for cooperative automated driving, an improvement in safety is expected for VRUs in a pedestrian crossing and a collision warning between vehicles resulting in the coordination of transport networks (e.g., enhancement in terms of vehicle position speed, driving trajectories, collision warnings, user comfort in traffic jams). Additionally, the use case will simultaneously integrate novel traffic management services for VRUs, such as safe passing, which reflects a red light onto the pavement preventing them to cross streets when they are distracted.

Considering the dedicated 5G networks, the following scenarios have been designed to progressively validate the technologies and CAM services in the cross-border corridor between the cities of Valka and Valga.

Considering the characteristics of the intersections, the time required to receive the authorisations from the local authorities, as well as the equipment needed, the development and evaluation of the C-ITS systems and services consider:

- firstly, the assessment and validation of the performance indicators in the intersection located in Valka city as well as the testing of the safety features enabled.
- once the required traffic equipment is installed in the Valga intersection (complete design and installation of the traffic equipment), then continue with the required evaluations.

The main KPI which will be assessed during the lab trials are end-to-end communication latency, reliability and bandwidth.

3.4.1.2 Roadmap of UC2.1 in the 5G-ROUTES project

Once the authorisations from local authorities to realize the installation of the required equipment on the chosen intersections in Valga and Valka cities are received, the activities will focus on the testing of the systems, as well as in the deployment of the safety features.

Considering the progressive implementation of traffic management services, the results from each evaluation will feed the next lab or field trial to be tested.

- Verification of Network and infrastructure (Smart crossings, smart light system): lab trial #1 and field trial #1.
- Basic features testing of the traffic equipment installed, e.g., data acquisition from the video monitoring system (Traffic light forecast/ traffic light assistant): Field trial #1 and Lab trial #2.

- Transmission and receipt of C-ITS messages, such as CPM, SPATEM (Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message), etc. (Multimodal monitoring): Lab trial #2, field trial #3.
- Functional verification of the safety features enabled at intersection level, e.g., Traffic Light Forecast\Traffic Light Assistant, Imminent Signal Violation Warning, Multi-modal Monitoring, etc. : field trial #3.
- Final validation of results considering the data resulted from the safety features enabled in both intersections (i.e., Valka and Valga): field trial #3.

3.4.1.3 Components

Regarding the intersections in the cities of Valka and Valga, the following list specifies the equipment to be installed.

Table 10: Components used in UC2.1.

Equipment	Model	Total Quantity	Estonia - Valga Intersection	Latvia - Valka Intersection
Traffic signal controller	ITC-3	2	1	1
Traffic Lights	Combia – CILANE	6	6	0
SafeLight System	Combia CILANE	14	6	8
Roadside Unit	Cohda MK5	2	1	1
Swarm Analytic Sensors	Swarm Perception Box OP100	2	1	1
AI Cameras	Hikvision	4	2	2
5G Router	XR80 Sierra Wireless	2	1	1

3.4.1.4 Sequence Diagram

UC 2.1 considers a reliable exchange of information through a 5G network enabling safety features for VRUs and autonomous vehicles. To do so, UC2.1 expects to use the enablers developed under the 5G-ROUTES project and integrated in the 5G platform, which at the same time allow the interchange of information with UC3.1 and UC3.3. The figure below presents the flow of information between the installed equipment, the 5G platform as well as the use cases involved in the testing.

Figure 29: 5G-ROUTES Project - UC2.1 Information Flow and synergies with UC3.1 and UC3.3

3.4.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The field trials will be performed in the city of Valka. The selected intersection in this location considers the installation of additional equipment (i.e., cameras, swarm analytic sensors, traffic light controller, RSU) which have been agreed with local authorities. The local authorities provided the requested authorisations to complete the installation activities, which were finalised later in 2022 in Valga and Valka. Simultaneously, as the intersection in Valga city requires a complete installation of the traffic equipment as well as the systems, a traffic study has been performed to define an optimal traffic signal control in function of the constantly changing traffic demand.

Table 11: Challenges during the lab trials and field trials

	Lab trial #1	Lab trial # 2	Lab trial # 3	Localized Trial #1	Localized Trial #2	Extended trial #3
Description	Verification of Network and infrastructure	Transmission and receipt of C-ITS messages	Data gathering and analysis	Data Acquisition from the video monitoring system	Aggregation of information and analysis	Final validation and analysis of information
Location	TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn) – Taltech			Valga-Valka cities		
Milestone	Validate initial architecture / Ensure the communication between the systems	Enable the cloud platform for data analysis and predictive algorithms.	Final validation	Scenario trials / data reception and transmission Technical verification of the pilot	Enable safety features at intersection level (VRUs, vehicles) Functional verification	Final Validation
Challenges	Service continuity considering the cross-border scenario	Assure the transmission of data to test the predictive algorithms on the cloud platform	Data analysis considering the continuity of the service in the cross-border	Technical verification of the C-ITS systems considering the video monitoring	Assure the transmission of information between the center and the objects on the road	

3.4.3 Lab Trial Results

3.4.23.4.1.3The lab trials involved the validation of the architecture that ensures the communication between the cooperative intelligent transport systems (C-ITS). This process has considered a technical verification of the functionality, and interoperability of the C-ITS systems, taking into account the video monitoring capabilities. However, some aspects related to the video monitoring systems still need to be finalized, such as the quality and privacy of the video data. Therefore, further testing and evaluation will be conducted to ensure that the video monitoring systems meet the requirements and standards of the C-ITS domain.

Figure 30: Valga Intersection – Video Monitoring System with vehicles trajectories

3.4.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.4):

Table 12: Field trial readiness for UC2.1

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Infrastructure related issues	4	0	2	1	71%
External servers	2	0	2	2	50%
UE related issues	6	0	5	3	62%
Tenant Web Portal	4	0	0	4	50%
V2X broker	0	0	1	4	10%
Enabler related issues	4	0	1	8	35 %
5G network related issues	2	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	5	0	0	0	100%
Privacy and security issues	0	0	1	0	60%
Total	16	0	5	11	58%

3.4.5 Next Steps

As the road infrastructure equipment has been installed in Valga and Valga cities, the next steps of the UC2.1 are focalized to:

- Verify the data acquisition from the video monitoring systems;
- Aggregate and analyze data to enable the safety features (VRUs, vehicles);
- Perform a functional testing of the C-ITS systems with the enablers (i.e., V2X Broker);
- Exchange V2X messages with UC3.1 and UC3.3 to evaluate the enablers of the CAM Services Platform;
- Final validation and analysis of the CAM services provided.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC3.1 and UC3.3 in a single use case “Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving”. The use case will be integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform for deployment of the CAM services used by the use case and to assure service continuity when crossing borders.

3.5 UC2.2 Traffic Jam Chauffeur

Important note: this use-case is planned to be discontinued. The contents of this section have been left intact to reflect the state of progress in June 2022.

3.5.1 Use Case Overview

The goal of UC2.2 is to assist vehicle passengers in and around traffic jams by providing remote detection of traffic jams in addition to automatic cruising (Figure 31).

Figure 31: UC2.2 visualization.

3.5.1.1 Use Case Description

The use case uses the same metrics as UC1.1 (section 3.1.1). The first field trial will be used to test aspects that are common to all EDI use cases (UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC2.2). In addition to common aspects, the following scenarios are planned to be tested for UC2.2:

1. **Slow deceleration towards detected traffic jam:** test the vehicle’s ability to decelerate slowly and evenly after having detected a distant traffic jam.
2. **Low-speed trajectory-following:** test the vehicle’s ability to follow its intended trajectory while taking nearby vehicles into account.

3.5.1.2 Roadmap of UC2.2 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

Similar to UC1.1 and UC1.2, the long-term trial plan for UC2.2 is to gradually increase its complexity. The first trial will be used to test a simple traffic jam scenario to test trajectory-following and localisation functions. The plan for further trials is to extend the scenarios with road signs, traffic lights and other on-road elements that have to be reacted to. In addition, the mechanism for detecting and reacting to a distant traffic jam will also be considered in greater detail.

3.5.1.3 Components

The following components are relevant for a complete execution and evaluation of UC2.2:

- Connected autonomous vehicle (CAV) on-board unit (OBU) by EDI:
 - DbW system (vehicle actuation)
 - Radar (lateral and longitudinal distance measurement)
 - 5G modem (kinematics data exchange)
 - Automotive grade computation platform (main computing unit)
 - Power equipment (for powering computer and peripherals)
 - LIDAR + GPS RTK (produce HD maps and localise vehicle in them)
 - Array of cameras (semantic interpretation of surroundings)
- Software (EDI CCAM platform):
 - vehicle control system (control algorithms reporting to DbW system)
 - MQTT client (transmission and reception inter-vehicle data)
 - CAN drivers and other interfaces
 - Autoware platform for additional manoeuvres based on HD maps
- MQTT broker (server and software)

Refer to D3.3 for more information on components and architecture.

3.5.1.4 Sequence Diagram

At the time of writing, the expected solution for integrating camera-based vision into EDI's Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform is to leverage existing *Autoware* functionalities. Hence, the sequence diagram below is very similar to the one shown in subsection 3.2.1.4 (UC1.2).

Figure 32: UC2.2 communication and control sequence diagram.

3.5.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

Refer to 3.1.2 (UC1.1) for information about trial locations.

EDI's use case verification strategy involves performing separate tests for different hardware and software components (DbW system, MQTT communication, vehicle control algorithms, etc.) before moving on to more complex tests that combine several functionalities at once (e.g., DbW actuation from control signals that have been obtained via MQTT). This ultimately leads to final verification tests that are as close in execution to the use cases as currently possible.

3.5.3 Lab Trial Results

The following table describes additional tests performed for UC2.2 that are not covered by UC1.1 and UC1.2 tests.

Table 13: List of already performed tests for UC2.2.

Test specification	Description
Preliminary camera stream acquisition test	Integrate array of cameras into vehicle and acquire camera data using the OBU with Nvidia PX2.
Camera-based detection	Apply AI-based algorithms on vehicle camera streams to recognise traffic elements.
Radar-based emergency braking	Test emergency-brake function upon detecting a pedestrian (tested with a mannequin, as shown in Figure 33).

Figure 33: Brake-test setup with a mannequin.

3.5.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.5):

Table 14: Field trial readiness for UC2.2

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	7	0	2	0	89%
OBU related issues	5	0	4	1	70%
External servers	4	0	2	0	83%
UE related issues	16	0	8	1	80%
CAM services	0	0	6	0	50%
Tenant Web Portal	4	0	0	4	50%
Enabler related issues	4	0	0	4	50%
5G network related issues	1	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	4	0	0	0	100%
Total	24	0	8	5	76%

For the context of the first trial phase, a large part of the results described in 3.1.4 are equally relevant for UC2.2. The following points can be noted about results specific for UC2.2:

- **Vehicle related issues:** while the localisation and detection functionalities of cameras and lidars have been validated, they are yet to be tested as part of a control loop.
- **Privacy and security:** for this use-case, there are no privacy-related issues, as the optical sensors are only supposed to yield metadata like classes and lane marking information, without transmitting any personalized data.

3.5.5 Next Steps

The next steps for UC2.2 involve fully integrating lidar measurements and HD-maps into EDI CCAM platform (also used by UC1.2) and adjusting the existing control loop to handle slow-approaching towards a traffic jam and low-speed trajectory-following, planned to be finished in early Q3/2022.

However, during the refocusing of the project, it was decided to discontinue work on this use case.

3.6 UC3.1 Sensor Info Sharing for Cooperative Situation Awareness

3.6.1 Use Case Overview

3.6.1.1 Use Case Description

Through communication with infrastructure and other vehicles, connected vehicles can enhance the perception of their environment beyond what their own sensors can detect so as to have a more holistic view of the local situation. The use case builds upon work performed in other projects and ongoing work within ETSI, regarding the collective perception of objects. Collective perception is based on the exchange of metadata of objects, such as relative position, speed, class and size. The observations are transmitted to other users in the area, which update their local dynamic map based on the information received.

The scenarios for the use case are described in D4.1. During the first set of lab trials, sensor sharing between two vehicles using the V2X routing service, deployed at VTT's network in Oulu, are tested. Both the cases where the vehicles are connected to the same V2X routing service and connected to two different networks are tested.

The main KPI which is tested during the lab trials is end-to-end communication latency.

3.6.1.2 Roadmap of UC3.1 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

During the first lab trials and the first field trials, the main focus is on the exchange of CPM messages between different road users. UC3.1 will also work together with UC2.1 and UC3.3 and exchange messages with the users involved in these use cases.

During the second lab trial tests and field trials, more challenging scenarios will be tested, in which the same user is detected by multiple sensors (i.e. from the infrastructure; UC2.1) and from an end-user device (UC3.3) and the application will be integrated with the 5G-ROUTES platform. Slicing will also be addressed, and its impact on the performance will be evaluated.

During the third set of lab trials the use case will be integrated with automated vehicles,

3.6.1.3 Components

The use case uses two OBUs, installed in two vehicles. The first OBU, consists of a detection unit, connected to a 5G modem. During the lab trials, modems which have been tested in other 5G related projects, were used, , such as Huawei CPE [26] and Netgear Nighthawk [25]. The detection software has been developed in previous projects, such as AI4DI [22], and the object detection is based on two sensors:

- camera: detection of objects using the AI tool YOLO [21] for detection and classification of objects. Based on YOLO the location of the object within the sensor field of view is determined.
- LIDAR: based on the LIDAR point data, in the bounding box of the camera object, the distance to the object, and hence the coordinates of the objects in the reference coordinate system of the vehicle are calculated.

Figure 34: OBU with detection unit, used in UC3.1

The detection unit (Figure 34) contains the LIDAR, camera, GNSS sensor and Jetson Xavier for processing. The 5G modem is placed in the vehicle, and both the detection unit and the modem are connected to an inverter in the car (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Detection unit installed on VTT's automated vehicle for test purposes

3.6.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 36 shows the sequence diagram for the implementation of UC3.1 during the first lab trials and the first set of field trials. The vehicles exchange the information using a single V2X broker, which is installed at VTT. During border crossing, there will be a short disruption in the service when the OBU switches from network and connects back to the V2X broker. During the second lab trials and the field trials there will be two instances of the V2X broker, which are part of the CAM Services Platform, developed by the 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 36: Sequence diagram for UC3.1 for the lab trial and the NSA field trials.

3.6.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The lab trials and verification tests were performed in VTT facilities in Tampere, Finland in March-June 2022. The V2X broker is implemented in Oulu and is connected to the 5GTN test network. The lab trials were concentrated on assuring that the use case performs as expected and to verify the end-to-end latency in a single 5G NSA test network, and that the V2X broker works as expected. Also, the situation that vehicles are connected to different networks was tested. The operation of the detection unit as well as the transmission of the CPM to another device were verified, while it was visually validated that the device was on the correct place.

3.6.3 Lab Trial Results

First, the performance of the detection program was verified, and information was exchanged between two devices. The first tests were performed using the WLAN (Wireless Local Area Network) network at the parking place of the VTT facilities at Tampere in March 2022. A person walked in front of the detection unit, and CPM information was sent via the V2X broker in Oulu to the person's laptop which was connected to the WLAN network. Tests were performed in collaboration with the 5G-SAFE-PLUS project [23], together with partners of this project. The detection unit was mounted on a trailer. As object, a VRU dummy was used. Based on the detection, a CPM message is generated, which is transmitted to the V2X broker using commercial 4G/5G network, and the message is received in a vehicle. Figure 37 shows a screenshot of the MQTT influxdb dashboard of the V2X broker, totalling about 140 000 published messages during the test; about 20 messages/second under load.

Figure 37: Screenshot of the MQTT influxdb dashboard.

Two V2X broker instances were installed in different machines in VTT Oulu, to verify if data flows when vehicles are connected to different networks. The performance of the V2X brokers was verified in terms of end-to-end latency in a local network. In total two tests were performed: 1) latency test with a single broker (Figure 38), and 2) latency test with two brokers having an AMQP connection between them (Figure 39). The latency for both tests was measured by a subscriber and a publisher client, connected to a broker. A publisher was sending CPM messages with a typical payload of 4063 bytes with a message rate of 1 message per 100 ms. A publisher and subscriber were providing the timestamp of sending and receiving the message, allowing to calculate latency. For two-broker measurement, the brokers were deployed on different physical machines. Latency results are presented in Figure 40.

Figure 38: Single broker latency measurement setup.

Figure 39: Two-broker latency measurement setup.

Latency (ms) comparison of 1 broker vs 2 brokers

Figure 40: V2X broker latency test.

Table 15: Latency comparison between two setups.

	Average latency (ms)	Min latency (ms)	Max latency (ms)
Single broker	2.21	1.2	12.7
Two brokers	3.25	1.9	11.3

The latency of CPMs between the detection unit and a vehicle in a 5G network was tested at the parking place of VTT Oulu, where there is coverage of the 5GTN NSA test network, with use of a single V2X broker. Tests were performed with different modems in the vehicle, as the Mikrotik was not yet available for these tests: the Goodmill Systems W24 5G router [27], the Huawei CPE router and the Netgear Nighthawk router. The median latency between the detection unit and the receiving vehicle using the MEC varies between 12 ms (Huawei), 20 ms (Netgear) and 24 ms (Goodmill).

Figure 41: End-to-end latencies measured between detection device application and vehicle application

3.6.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

Table 16 gives an overview of the field trial readiness tests:

Table 16: Field trial readiness for UC3.1

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	7	0	0	0	100%
OBU related issues	9	0	0	0	100%
UE related issues	16	0	0	0	100%
Tenant Web Portal	6	0	0	2	75%
V2X broker	4	0	0	0	100%
Enabler related issues	10	0	0	2	83%
5G network related issues	1	0	0	0	100 %
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100 %
Network related issues	4	0	0	0	100 %
Total	30	0	0	2	94 %

The main results of the verification tests include:

- **Vehicle related issues:** for the first field trials, a box containing the LIDAR and camera will be placed on the vehicle. The algorithm for detection is based on previous work at VTT, and communication between two devices from VTT has been tested. The end-to-end latency was measured with different OBUs in a 5G NSA test network in static conditions (Figure 41).
- **OBU related issues:** the OBU has been tested, and communication between two VTT devices has also been tested. Interoperability with CPMs from other providers has been checked through off-line exchange of test CPM messages with the other partners in the project.
- **Tenant Web Portal:** the entry of KPIs has been tested, but starting and stopping of logging from the Tenant Web Portal has not yet been tested.
- **V2X broker:** the basic message exchange has been tested. The performance of the V2X broker has been tested, as described in the previous section.
- **5G network:** handover and roaming has been tested by the MNOs. The Mikrotik 5G router will be used for the field trial tests.
- **Privacy and security:** for this use case there are no privacy related issues, as only metadata will be exchanged, and only data of research vehicles in the trial site.

3.6.5 Next Steps

The logging for the use case will be further developed and tested prior to the trials in Latvia and Estonia.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC2.1 and UC3.3 in a single use case "Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving". The use case will be integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform for deployment of the CAM services used by the use case and to assure service continuity when crossing borders.

3.7 UC3.2 Connected Maintenance

Note: during the refocusing of the project in the Summer of 2022 it was decided to discontinue further work on this use case.

3.7.1 Use Case Overview

3.7.1.1 Use Case Description

In the Connected Maintenance use case, vehicles send On Board Diagnostics (OBD) to a central server (cloud server) which analyses the data in real time. This is a typical mMTC use case: critical aspects of mMTC systems

are the capacity/cost of the system; throughput and latency constraints are low enabling to improve reliability via retransmission.

For the Connected Maintenance, vehicles exchange information with a server, such as:

- Localisation information containing absolute position.
- The required bandwidth is the bandwidth to connect a car to the network, through MQTT type of service.
- Latency is the time between the transmission of a message and its reception in the server, ping roundtrip tests will be used for latency testing.
- Capacity is expressed as the number of vehicles per cell per MHz.
- Cross-border situation impact is evaluated based on service interruption time, latency and packet loss ratio when driving from Domain A to Domain B.

Figure 42: Architecture of UC3.2.

During the lab trials, the following scenarios are tested:

- Connectivity to the 5G network, network and service availability;
- Connectivity to the cloud server,
- Data upload to the cloud server.

The target KPIs measured during the tests will be as follows:

- *Round Trip Time (RTT)* - Loop latency is measured as the time between transmission and response at the same UE, ping tests.
- *Minimum granted throughput* - The data rate as perceived at the network layer between two selected end-points.

3.7.1.2 Roadmap of UC3.2 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

The use case 3.2 has started lab trials with NB-IoT connectivity in 4G LTE network. The next stage has been 5G NSA connectivity upgrade for the OBU. As there is no distinct NB-IoT service in 5G NSA network, common data service is used for OBU connectivity to cloud server.

The second lab trial tests include data upload to the cloud server, data filtering and post-processing for predictive maintenance as well as for driving style prediction.

The third set of lab trial tests include mobility and capacity simulation tests.

3.7.1.3 Components

The use case 3.2 OBU has been upgraded with 5G NR (New Radio) NSA connectivity and GNSS receiver. The components are shown on Figure 43 below. For the 5G NR NSA connectivity a MikroTik router is used. The OBU will be connected to the router through LAN (Local Area Network) cable. A GNSS receiver is connected to the OBU to get GPS positioning data. RTK functionality is planned to be added to the GPS receiver at a later stage. An OBDII reader is connected to the OBU through USB connection, in order to retrieve the sensor data from a vehicle. An inverter is used to provide power to the router. In order to improve parameter acquisition capability, an additional laptop is attached to the 5G NSA router. A data collection application for the laptop will be developed to facilitate data acquisition and storage.

Figure 43: Lab trials components in 5G NR NSA network.

3.7.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Within this use case, the OBU starts a network connection to the MQTT broker which is located at the cloud. After the network connection is established, a sensor data reading request is issued to the OBDII reader. The sensor data is sent back to the OBU, which will forward this data to the cloud. In the cloud the sensor data is collected and preprocessed. The preprocessed data is fed to a predictive Machine Learning algorithm, which will predict the car maintenance needs and the drivers' driving style estimation. The prediction data will be distributed to third party stakeholders. The sequence diagram is presented in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Lab trials components in 5G NR NSA network.

3.7.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

Lab trials have been performed in TTU campus area during February and March 2022. Initial tests have been performed with OBU attached to 4G LTE NB-IoT modem. The next tests, with the Mikrotik 5G NSA modem at 3,5GHz band were performed in March-May 2022. Telia 5G NR NSA test site is used for lab trials in TTU campus, Tallinn. In addition, cross-border tests were performed in Bikernieki in May 2022 using the Mikrotik 5G modem.

3.7.3 Lab Trial Results

Functionalities tested during lab trials with OBU with 4G LTE NB-IoT modem for the UC3.2 (data summary shown in Table 17):

- OBU functionality to read OBDII data from vehicle and filter the data,
- Sensor data connectivity testing to the cloud server through NB-IoT connection,
- NB-IoT network data measurements and reporting to the cloud,
- MQTT protocol configuration for the cloud services, Initial lab trials with a gasoline vehicle,
- GPS data collection and integration tests,
- Cloud MQTT functional tests,
- Data upload testing with MQTT with payload in SmartREST protocol,
- Latency ping tests.

Table 17: NB-IoT lab trials RTT ping test results.

	Inside building (no OBD data)	Inside car (no movement)	City driving
Duration (sec)	1795	1765	1596
Ping TX_count	702	653	530
Ping RX_count	702	653	530
Ping lost_count	0	0	1
Ping timeout_Count	0	97	221
Ping timeout_rate	0%	14.8%	41.8%

Ping avg_delay (ms)	470	428	453
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Functionalities tested with lab trials with 5G NR NSA modem at 3,5GHz band:

- Network coverage tests have been performed in TTU campus area at Telia test network (shown in Figure 45),
- Handover tests between multiple cells (the test site has 3 cells),
- Tests with a new 5G NSA modem (MikroTik router) performed.

Figure 45: 5G NR NSA coverage test during lab trials in TTU campus.

Figure 46: 5G NR NSA ping tests during lab trials in TTU campus

Figure 46 shows ping tests performed in 5G NSA network with MikroTik router. Ping test summary is shown in Table 18.

Table 18: 5G NSA lab trials RTT ping test results (MikroTik router).

Inside car (no movement)	
Duration (sec)	1690
Ping TX_count	1552
Ping RX_count	1552
Ping lost_count	0
Ping timeout_Count	0
Ping timeout_rate	0%
Ping avg_delay (ms)	18.49

3.7.4 Cross-border roaming tests in Bikernieki

Cross-border roaming was tested in the virtual cross-border in Bikernieki in May 2022. Roaming was tested by sending continuously ping messages from the OBU in a moving vehicle to a server located in Tallinn. The 5G modem used was the Mikrotik 5G router.

Figure 47 shows the latency for a vehicle moving from the Telia network to the LMT network with a Telia SIM. The latency in the home network (i.e., connected to the core in Tallinn) is on average 14 ms, the average latency in the visiting network is 40 ms. The network performance decreases while the latency increases prior to the handover, during which no network is passed.

Figure 47: Latency measurement (ping RTT) for vehicle moving across the border from the Estonian to the Latvian network

The network handover starts with a measurement event, e.g. and A2 event [30]. This event cannot directly be measured using ping messages, but it is assumed to occur when the latency increases substantially. Only after a handover preparation time of 12 seconds the user-plane is interrupted. The user-plane interruption time is 25 seconds, after which transfer of data is resumed.

Figure 48: Service interruption for ping transfer

3.7.5 Field Trial Readiness Verification

Table 19: Field trial readiness for UC3.2

Group	5	0	0	0	100%
Vehicle related issues	5	0	0	0	100%
OBU related issues	5	0	3	0	81%
External servers	5	0	0	0	100%
UE related issues	15	0	3	0	92%
Tenant Web Portal	4	0	0	4	50%
Enabler related issues	4	0	0	4	50%
5G network related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	4	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	7	0	0	0	100%
Privacy and security issues	0	0	0	1	0%
Total	26	0	3	5	81%

3.7.6 Next Steps

Tests for 5G NR NSA capacity tests will be performed as the final phase of lab trials.

During the refocusing of the project, it was decided to discontinue work on this use case.

3.8 UC3.3 VRU Collision Avoidance

3.8.1 Use Case Overview

3.8.1.1 Use Case Description

In the VRU collision avoidance use case, connected VRUs share their presence, while not connected VRUs can be detected by the infrastructure. Then, information about localisation of VRUs and vehicles is exchanged between road users using MEC services, so that, every participant, i.e., a VRU or a vehicle, is aware in real time of other users' location and motion dynamics and can adapt its behaviour appropriately to avoid a potential collision. As illustrated in Figure 49, V2X communication can support such an application by enabling:

- communication between VRUs and vehicles;
- deployment of smart intersection;
- perception sharing between vehicles.

As such an application requires a continuous update regarding the situation - such as location, speed, direction of travel of road users to smoothly anticipate any risk and avoid sudden emergency braking due to late detection - ensuring real-time communication and network availability is required in all conditions.

Figure 49: UC3.3 Schematic Description.

The following scenarios are planned to be tested during the three testing cycles of 5G-ROUTES project:

1. *Vehicle-Pedestrian Connectivity over 5G* to test the application correct connectivity over a real 5G Network Test in lab trial #1 and field trial #1.
2. *Infrastructure to vehicle connectivity over 5G* to test the connectivity between the vehicle and a smart infrastructure over a real 5G network Test in field trial #1.
3. *Test road hazard detection, i.e., dangerous situation between vehicle and pedestrian, with V2P (Vehicle to Pedestrian) Communication in 5G.* Test in lab trial #2 and field trial #2.
4. *VRU Collision Avoidance using 5G Connectivity* to test continuity of data flows between different entities (vehicles, pedestrian, infrastructure) under mobility conditions and with multiple users. Test in lab trial #3 and field trial #3.

3.8.1.2 Roadmap of VRU Collision Avoidance in the 5G-ROUTES Project

A summary of what is expected to be ready for each lab and field trial test is presented below.

- Lab trial #1: Transmission, receipt and processing of CAM/CPM, routing of messages through MECs.
- Field trial #1: Evaluation of performance of CAM/CPM exchange using a 5G NSA network at a cross-border.
- Lab trial #2: Performance of road hazard detection in more challenging environments (multiple sources for detection of the same object).
- Field trial #2: Evaluation of road hazard detection using different enablers (smart intersection, localisation of VRU using 5G) using a 5G SA network at a cross-border.
- Lab trial #3: Integration and final validation with vehicles and VRUs on different scenarios, e.g., performance of the system in case multiple VRUs are present.
- Field trial #3: Final validation. Tests in the cross-border corridor in intersections equipped with VRU detection systems and in road sections not-equipped with such dedicated infrastructure.

3.8.1.3 Components

For UC3.3, the CAV is equipped with an On-Board Unit (OBU) and 5G router for exchanging its current state on the network and the VRU is carrying a prototype device providing connectivity via its onboard 5G module. Both

devices can transfer information regarding their localization and can be alerted depending on the risk level via dedicated services.

Figure 50: Components of UC 3.3

More details about the functionalities of every component are listed below:

- CAV OBU
 - Cooperative Awareness Service is in charge of generating, encoding and decoding CAM;
 - MQTT Client is in charge of sending and receiving data packets;
 - VRU Collision risk assessment is responsible for evaluating if any VRU present a risk to collide with the CAV.
- VRU Device
 - Cooperative Awareness Service responsible for generating, encoding and decoding of CAM transferred messages;
 - MQTT client service handling the communication with the MQTT broker (connection and publication and reception of data messages);
 - VRU warning service is responsible for constantly evaluating collision risks related to the VRU, based on the perception achieved by the received awareness messages and triggering warnings to the user if necessary;
 - basic HMI warnings implementation including audio and visual signals.
- V2X Broker
 - Server accessible in the network for exchanging data messages between the different entities.

3.8.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Within the use case, both CAV and VRU gain awareness by relying on the developed components. Figure 51 illustrates the data flow between CAV and VRU to monitor collision risks through exchange of V2X messages (CAM – Cooperative Awareness Message) while CAV is crossing the border.

In this use case, both users connect to their home 5G network and can share their status using CAM published on V2X brokers. By subscribing to the messages published in their current geographical tiles, the CAV can consume V2X messages sent by the VRU (similarly the VRU can consume V2X messages produced by the CAV). Upon the border crossing, the CAV loses its connectivity with its home network and need to reconnect to the visiting network.

In the first trials, V2X brokers are deployed in public internet, thus, the CAV reconnects to the V2X broker available using the endpoint of its home country to continue receiving V2X messages from the VRU. Here, service interruption is recognized by the loss of connectivity with 5G network and lasts until CAV has reconnected to the V2X broker. During, this period, CAMs sent from the VRU device are lost due to the disconnection of receiver on the CAV.

Figure 51: Sequence diagram for UC3.3.

3.8.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

As illustrated in Figure 52, UC components were tested at VEDECOM facilities in Versailles Satory, France, where access to a test track equipped with private 5G Network and a full coverage by a 5G Commercial network is provided.

In addition, the trial site is equipped with roadside equipment (cameras / LIDAR) to test the behaviour of use case components when interacting with the infrastructure and for monitoring purposes.

First offline tests have been conducted to ensure compatibility between different entities (Vehicle and VRU). Then remote laboratory tests have been done to validate the capabilities of different devices (OBU and VRU).

Test specification	Description	Type	Related checklist item	Main result
VRU position and dynamics	VRU device is able to generate CAM from embedded GNSS	Remote laboratory	D5	C-ITS Protocol stack of VRU device is able to access MQTT broker and publish encoded CAM (OK)
Integration of CAM issued by VRU in VEDECOM vehicle	OBU installed in vehicle, and CAM sent from VRU device. OBU is able to decode CAM and provide the information to supervision system for risk assessment	Remote laboratory	V1, V2, V13, V18 S1, S2, S3, S4, S5	C-ITS Protocol stack of vehicle OBU is able to receive CAM published by VRU device using MQTT broker (OK)
Integration of CAM issued by vehicle in VRU device	OBU installed in vehicle, and CAM sent from vehicle to VRU device. VRU device is able to decode CAM and provide the information to assess collision risk	Remote laboratory	D1, D5 S1, S2, S3, S4, S5	C-ITS Protocol stack of VRU device is able to receive CAM published by vehicle using MQTT broker (OK)
VRU collision risk assessment	Upon the detection of VRU from the system anticipates any collision risk with VRU and issues an appropriate message/instruction to avoid any accident.	Outdoor tests	V4, V11, V12, V19, V20,	Notification of the presence of VRU at the vehicle side after the reception of message.
VRU alert system	Upon the detection of vehicle approaching towards the VRU and alert is raised for the user	Outdoor tests	D2, D4, D6	Warning to the VRU received when vehicle is approaching
Logging and metric calculation	Vehicle and VRU can log application related information to assess performances	Offline - Postprocessing	V10, V22, D8 ET1, ET3, ET4, ET5, ET6, ET7, ET8	Both OBU and VRU device store application logs as csv files during the tests. Use case can be configure in the Tenant Web Portal (TWP) and application logs can be uploaded in the TWP.

Full lab trials have been performed in April 2022 with UC components developed for the first iteration of trials. Both CAV and VRU device were present on the test site with 5G connectivity capabilities, as illustrated in Figure 53 and Figure 54. They were connected to 5G NSA Public Network and could exchange data using a MQTT broker

deployed in the facilities of the laboratory test site. Additionally, Figure 55 shows on a map the different path taken by the vehicle and location of the VRU during the trials.

Figure 53: VRU equipment for UC3.3 used during lab trials

Figure 54: Equipment installed in vehicle for UC3.3 lab trials

Figure 55: Geographical path of vehicle (green) and location of VRU (red) during the tests

To validate UC components, multiple iterations have been performed with the CAV approaching towards the VRU. Figure 56 illustrated the results of 4 iterations from the perspective of both CAV and VRU.

First, based on the reception of Cooperative Awareness Message issued by the VRU, CAV can assess the distance remaining before the collision. Second, as the VRU device also receives Cooperative Awareness Message from the CAV, it can trigger alert to the user. As shown, on the right axis of the figure below, different levels of alert have been implemented depending on the estimated risk.

Figure 56: Results of applications for UC obtained during different iterations

To prepare for the field trials, logs have been collected at the application and message level to assess performance of the network with the UC.

Figure 57 shows the distribution of end-to-end latency measured at the reception of messages by the CAV. During, these tests median value have been measured to be 116ms, which is above the expected values. In the next trials, it is expected that this value could be decreased by the deployment of 5G SA network and CAM service platform.

Figure 58 shows the distribution of packet delivery ratio calculated based on 30s time slots during the trials. Here, the results shows that more than 99.5 packets are correctly received for more than 90% of the assessed time windows.

Figure 57: Distribution of end-to-end latency measured during the exchange of Cooperative Awareness Messages between CAV and VRU

Figure 58: Distribution of packet delivery ratio for Cooperative Awareness Messages measured at both CAV (green) and VRU (red)

3.8.4 Cross-border roaming tests in Bikernieki

Roaming was tested for UC3.3 in Bikernieki. In the test V2X messages were sent by the VRU device to VTT's V2X broker, which distributed it to a UE in a vehicle crossing the virtual border. The vehicle UE used the Mikrotik 5G router.

Table 21: Tests performed in Bikernieki to test component readiness in UC3.3

Test specification	Description	Type	Related checklist item	Main result
On site 5G Connectivity test	Vehicle and VRU are connected to different 5G networks and can exchange safety related messages	Outdoor test	EV1, EV2, EV3, EV4 N1, N2, N3	Both vehicle and VRU can connect respectively in Telia and LMT 5G NSA networks. They exchange CAM messages through 2 V2X routers deployed in VTT facilities
On site cross-border scenario	Vehicle is approaching the VRU and crosses the border, i.e it changes from its home network to a visiting network.	Outdoor test	N5, N7	Cross border is forced by switching off Telia gNb. Vehicle attach to LMT network after few seconds when using a Mikrotik 5G router. Test also conducted with multi-SIM solution from Goodmill, no interruption is observed with this setup.

Figure 59 (left) shows the end-to-end latency from the moment of message generation until the receipt at the UE in the vehicle. There is an interruption time of about 3 seconds before getting again messages from the V2X broker. Prior to the border crossing there is a degradation in the latency.

It has to be noted that in this case the method for changing the network was different as in the tests for UC3.2: the Telia base station was switched off, to have the roaming with LMT, instead of having real roaming.

Figure 59 (right) shows the data rate. In normal conditions, 10 messages of 42 bytes are received per second. After connection break, messages which are buffered in the broker, are received, causing a peak in the data rate.

Figure 59: End-to-end latency and received data rate from VRU message generation to receipt at the vehicle crossing the border

3.8.5 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.8):

Table 22: Field trial readiness for UC3.3

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	8	0	0	0	100%
OBU related issues	10	0	0	0	100%
External servers	5	0	0	0	100%
Other end user devices	7	0	0	0	100%
UE related issues	30	0	0	0	100%
Tenant Web Portal	7	0	0	1	88%
V2X broker	4	0	0	1	80%
Enabler related issues	11	0	0	2	85%
5G network related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	6	0	0	0	100%
Total	47	0	0	2	96%

As can be seen in Table 22, the main verification tests have been focused on the issues related to user equipment. Static and dynamic tests are completed successfully to validate UE related issues.

During the lab trial, availability of V2X message router in the cloud has been confirmed so that it can be used with the use case components during the trials. Availability of Tenant Web Portal has been confirmed with the possibility to create test scenarios and upload results from data logs taken directly on the user equipment. As shown in the previous section some KPIs such as end-to-end latency and reliability can be measured from the current logs. Calculation of other KPIs is still under progress and should be updated for next iterations.

Finally, 5G network has been tested in Bikernieki racetrack with the UC equipment but not tested in the test site of Valka/Valga during lab trials. This will be done before starting the field trials on that test site.

3.8.6 Next Steps

UC components for the first iteration have been validated in the closed site and are ready to be validated in the final trial site in order to start the trial period on 5G NSA. The equipment is ready to collect measurement and some offline processing is being developed for the calculation and upload of KPIs on Tenant Web Portal.

During the refocusing of the project, the use case was combined with UC3.1 and UC3.3 in a single use case “Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving”. In addition, the use case is refocused on “Collision warning with mobile roadwork operation”, in which the devices described above are used to identify mobile roadwork equipment. Work also includes deployment of the CAM service, which provides the warning to road users, in the CAM Services Platform. The use case will be integrated with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform for deployment of the CAM services, which are used by the use case, and to assure service continuity when crossing borders.

3.9 UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go

3.9.1 Use Case Overview

3.9.1.1 Use Case Description

Use case 4.1 consists of a collaborative augmented reality game in which players have to locate and interact with virtual elements that are placed in the real space and move around them.

Players point the camera in different directions, in order to find the AR elements, and see them through the augmented reality view on screen. Virtual elements are shown integrated in the real scene captured by the smartphone camera. Every item is located based on GPS coordinates so the player finds them thanks to the device embedded GPS, compass, and inertial sensors.

The virtual elements are common to all users who are playing the same game session, and they see those elements located in the same positions in the real world regardless of the position of each player, thanks to the fact that both participants and virtual elements will be geolocated.

Lab trial scenario 1: Test the application over a 5G network in CTTC testbed facility. Analyse and adjust application features to solve 5G compatibility issues.

On this first field trial, the objective is to check the compatibility of the game in a 5G NSA environment. The main goal is to have the game working in a laboratory controlled environment and check the response of the different parts involved.

Server and network performance measurements are taken locally in order to ensure the enough capabilities of the network for the correct playing of the game.

Lab trial scenario 2: Find the containerized application working limits. Stress the network and the application until failing conditions and then sample system related measurements.

Since the behaviour and complexity of the game is modulable and in a certain way adaptable to the conditions that the network allows, the objective of these lab trial is to find if the network limitations are high enough to allow smooth and efficient game play after the containerization. For this, different configurations that require different network capacities (latency, bandwidth, and calculation times) are tested, looking for the most suitable for the correct functioning of the game and for the poorest situation where the systems keep working properly. Measurements of all these tests are taken to later analyse the efficiency of the 5G network in different conditions.

Lab trial scenario 3: Final application overall functionality. Check that all the pipeline modules and workflow of the application work flawlessly.

The plan of this last scenario is to test all the functionalities needed for the correct full game behaviour, replicating all real environmental conditions, including disconnection simulation for border crossing. The testing specifications for this scenario are improved when scenarios 1 and 2 tests will be finished, and their results analysed.

3.9.1.2 Roadmap of Immersive Multiuser Gaming on the Go in the 5G-ROUTES Project

The objective of the first field trials is to check the readiness on the client application and the server to work correctly in a 5G environment. The first field trials are planned to be performed on the already available 5G NSA network; therefore part of the network components corresponds to the infrastructure of a commercially available 4G network.

For future trials, in addition to including the different enablers developed in the project and expanding the tests to include elements such as servers on the edge, on roaming tests and border crossing, it will also be interesting to compare these results with the current ones, to determine which improvements are detected when moving from a current commercial network infrastructure to a specific infrastructure for 5G.

3.9.1.3 Components

UC4.1 incorporates the following main components:

Figure 60: UC4.1 Lab trial components

Game server: Containerized service (Ubuntu 20.04), which is deployed during the 5G SA field trials in the CAM Services Platform, connected to the 5G network core, in charge to make the game scene calculations, receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game, and finally updating all connected devices accordingly.

5G Android Smartphone: runs the game client, devices must have GPS, compass and rear camera. The game is played in these devices, where the user can see the scene environment and interact with the elements included. For basic testing one smartphone is enough, but the ideal is to use two or three for the testing.

5G Network connection: Communication between smartphones and game server is finally performed over a 5G network environment.

3.9.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 61: Sequence diagram of UC4.1 (Multiuser gaming on the go).

3.9.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The laboratory tests have been carried out both locally in the Brainstorm offices in Valencia and in the 5G laboratories of the CTTC in Barcelona, during the months from March to May 2022.

Given the low complexity of the infrastructure for this use case, the verification for the preparation of the field trials is quite simple.

First, it is necessary to verify the correct and fluid communication between server and client, verifying that the connection is stable and, secondly, validate the conditions present in the network, for the latter measurement, both on the client and server sides, of real-time performance statistics that will be recorded (latency, processing time, data sent/received, messages per second...). In addition to displaying this data in real time, during the execution of the application the client also saves it locally for later analysis.

3.9.3 Lab Trial Results

Remote server test: The first test, done in March 2022 focused on testing the server virtualized (installed in a VM, still not containerized) for correct behaviour and performance. This test has been performed already by connecting remotely from Brainstorm office in Valencia to CTTC laboratories in Barcelona through a VPN (Virtual Private Network) connection to check the readiness of the server. The client in this case has been a Unity Engine project emulating the game behaviour. After solving basic configuration issues, the tests were successful.

Local tests: Tests performed locally in Barcelona CTTC laboratories during end March and begin of April 2022, with a physical smartphone device connected to the containerized game server, with the objective to take and store network performance measurements.

Tenant Web: During June 2022, as the Tenant Web started to be available, trials of manual access and data reporting have been done, concluding these tests satisfactorily in the absence of automatic access to the server through the APIs.

Handover: Some tests about application reconnection have been performed but using only one network provider and simulating the handover disconnecting manually the network connection of the device. The results have been successful, getting very low reconnection times from the application side when connection is recovered (less than 250 milliseconds). It has not yet been possible to carry out handover tests on a real infrastructure.

Results:

The results obtained are shown in Table 23; the characteristics are satisfactory, however, better performance is expected in future tests, when more components of the 5G SA network become available.

Table 23: Results of lab trials for UC4.1

Server frames per second	180 – 200 fps
End-to-end latency	60 – 80 ms
Server income data	4-5 kbps
Server outcome data	350 kbps
Server processing time	1 – 2 ms
Client reconnection time	< 250 ms

3.9.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.9):

Table 24: Field trial readiness for UC4.1

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Other end user devices	4	0	2	0	83%
UE related issues	4	0	2	0	83%
CAM services	6	0	0	0	100%
Tenant Web Portal	5	0	0	2	71%
Enabler related issues	5	0	0	2	71%
5G network related issues	0	0	0	1	75%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	3	0	0	1	75%
Total	18	0	2	3	83%

The performed UC 4.1 tests have been carried out both in Brainstorm’s own offices and in the CTTC laboratories. During the first trials a dedicated server has been used to manage the game’s services in both locations. After the service containerization the trials have been carried out employing the service running on docker system and later, after its adaptation for the CAM repository, on the Kubernetes cluster. Preliminary tests have been carried out on a game prototype simulating several simultaneous clients with satisfactory results. The tests carried out on wired commercial networks, VPNs and the laboratory, have resulted in a correct functioning of the game with connection to the server in real time and very low latencies that allow it to function correctly, which will allow comparing the results obtained with those of the next field tests.

Tests of automatic disconnection and reconnection of the game to the server have also been carried out, and after several iterations this reconnection time has been reduced to a minimum under local networks, which guarantees that the MNO change test can be carried out later during the field trials.

The correct visualisation and saving of the network, server and game statistics that will be used for the calculation of the KPIs has also been verified.

3.9.5 Next Steps

The expected next steps are the connection with all the enablers that the project infrastructure provides. First the implementation of MQTT communication as the project infrastructure (focused on CAM) requires. This will allow the communication with the other infrastructure components.

As the game client transmits the data to the game server employing a proprietary protocol, the communication with the enablers will be implemented replicating the operations that a common car OBU is carrying out. The implementation and codification of CAM messages and their transmission/reception to/from the V2X broker will allow: the clients monitorization by the resources allocation and management system (PRAE), the communication with the integration fabric (IF), allowing the reception of experiment start, experiment ID and stop experiment parameters to synchronise all the experimental operations along all the clients and services involved. Moreover, the communication with the assisted service continuity (ASC), that allows to receive the information needed by the clients to connect to their service when entering the visiting domain, will be tested. Finally, the delivery of the collected KPIs to the TWP, employing the post API, will be tested as soon as this functionality will be available. The replication of the OBUs communication employing a SW prototype will also allow the simulation in lab, of GPS tracks at the final experimental locations, hence testing in this way allows a real positional situation but in silico conditions.

3.10 UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move

3.10.1 Use Case Overview

3.10.1.1 Use Case Description

Use case 4.2 consists of a real-time virtual conference session where a presenter, captured with stereoscopic cameras on a green screen set, is transmitted to VR headsets of the audience, and embedded in a virtual scenario. This setup allows the presenter to show 3D animated content to the viewers and get feedback from the same audience. The viewers are allowed, employing the VR headset controllers, to point to virtual environment elements and, by means of voice-notes, post questions and get response from the remote presenter.

The use case will provide the required means for the presenter to be stereoscopically captured and inserted in virtual scenarios including immersive graphic elements to improve presentation's dynamics and to allow presenter and consumers to communicate between each other on specific details of the surrounding virtual scenario.

Lab trial scenario 1: Verify that all the interconnected systems are working properly over a 5G network in CTC testbed facility. Discover and adjust application features in order to solve 5G compatibility issues.

On this first field trial, the objective is to check the compatibility of the streamed video content in a 5G NSA environment. The main goal is to adjust the presenter acquisition and video content stream to work properly in a laboratory controlled environment and check the reliability of the different systems involved.

The system verification and adjustment phase imply some measurements that are taken on bitrate and data throughput. The scope of the tests is to adjust the different communication features to the network requirements and obtain the first functional streaming system configuration compatible with 5G network features and getting advantage of them.

Lab trial scenario 2: Find the application working limits. Stress the network and the streaming application (increasing frame rate and resolution) until not optimal conditions (the stream is played back not fluidly) and measure system related indicators.

The streaming features can be modulated, starting from a single non-stereo stream until 4K stereo. The objective of this lab trial is to find if the network features are capable to allow for smooth and efficient stream playback. For this experiment, different configurations (framerate, resolution, mono or stereo video modality) are tested,

to establish the most suitable adjustment for content acquisition and streaming. During these tests throughput and E2E latency are sampled to later analyse the efficiency of the 5G network in different conditions.

Lab trial scenario 3: This trial will test the first complete version of the system including audience feedback to the presenter. This version will allow to quantify the delay of the audience feedback to the presenter in order to understand if adjustments are needed to have the system working properly and have reliable session interactions for a real virtual meeting. Also, it will check that all the pipeline and workflow of the application works flawlessly.

Verify the whole system's features, already tested in the previous trials, adding the feedback stage and measure the performance of the involved systems to detect available improvements needed for videoconferencing system working properly. Replicate all real environment conditions, including disconnection simulation for border crossing. The testing specifications for this scenario will be improved when scenarios 1 and 2 tests are finished, and their results analysed.

3.10.1.2 Roadmap of 3D Real-time Virtual Collaboration on the Move in the 5G-ROUTES Project

The objective on the lab trials is to check progressively the readiness of the different systems involved in a 5G environment. The multicast service that distributes the content to the viewers and should be deployed on edge, is containerized employing docker. This condition should be tested deeply, first on docker platform and later managed inside the Kubernetes environment.

For future trials, in addition to the implementation of the different enablers' employment developed in the project, the tests will be varied simulating all the operations that need to be completed to migrate the clients from one domain to the other and that can be tested in a lab environment. Comparison of the results obtained in lab settings with those recorded during the field trials will be done to determine which improvements are detected when the application and related operations are executed in a cabled local network infrastructure (best network configuration) to the mobile 5G infrastructure.

3.10.1.3 Components

Figure 62: UC4.2 Components

Acquisition and streaming server: Standalone capturing station cabled to the 5Gcore. This hardware stage includes a connected stereoscopic camera that captures the presenter on the green screen setup. This system is in charge of sampling frames from the capturing camera and pack them for streaming directly to the VR player at the other side of the 5G connection. Also, for testing, the possibility to use a pre-recorded video stream server is explored, in order to avoid the need of real-time recordings continuously.

Video Proxy Server: Service that provides the bridge between the acquisition and streaming server and the mobile (laptops) clients. The service multicasts the video content coming from the source and multiplies it based on the number of clients. This service is migrated to the visiting domain.

5G Modem: To connect the client side to the network, and because the virtual reality headsets currently available on the market do not allow a direct connection to the 5G network, an intermediate interface is needed. For this, a 5G Modem and a featured laptop ia used.

Laptop: On the one hand, it is used as an interface to connect the 5G modem and the virtual reality headset, but also it also performs the final scene rendering to be sent to the headset. The laptop is used to decompress the video and integrate the presenter into the virtual scene, leaving the headset for now only as the display interface. For this reason, customers who do not have access to a VR headset can also attend the presentation directly through a laptop.

VR Headset: Connected to the laptop, responsible to capture the user headtracking and interaction, and also responsible to visualise the virtual environment render.

3.10.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 63: Sequence diagram of UC4.2 – Collaborative conference on the go.

3.10.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The laboratory tests have been carried out both locally in the Brainstorm offices in Valencia and in the 5G laboratories of the CTTC in Barcelona, during the months from March to May 2022.

Given the low complexity of the infrastructure for this use case, the verification for the preparation of the field trials is quite simple.

First, it is necessary to verify the correct and fluid video transmission from the server to the client, verifying that the connection is stable, and secondly, validate the conditions present in the network. For the latter, both on the client and server sides, real-time performance statistics are recorded (data sent/received, video bit-rate, frames per second, resolution, application latency), and the client saves all this data locally for later analysis, in addition to displaying it in real time during the execution of the application.

3.10.3 Lab Trial Results

Video transmission tests: These tests, performed during April 2022, consisted of checking the correct video transmission between the presenter side and the client side through the 5G testbed infrastructure, and testing several video configurations in order to check the best quality without network issues.

Tenant Web: During June 2022, as the Tenant Web became available, the reporting of KPIs related to clients and the service have been tested employing the files manual upload. The tests got positive results but the implementation of automatic access to the server through the APIs is needed to simplify the experimental operations and will be tested as soon as available.

Handover: Some tests about application reconnection have been performed but using only one network provider and simulating the handover disconnecting manually the network connection of the device. The results, in this case, were unsuccessful and as the reconnection time greater (greater than 5 seconds) than what the application can manage due the high requirements of the video transmission. Further work on this aspect is still needed.

3.10.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

The following table gives an overview of the checklist testing status, details of which can be found in Annex 1 (Section 6.10):

Table 25: Field trial readiness for UC4.2.

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
External servers	6	0	0	0	100%
Other end user devices	4	0	2	0	83%
UE related issues	10	0	2	0	92%
Tenant Web Portal	5	0	0	3	63%
Enabler related issues	5	0	0	3	63%
5G network related issues	0	0	0	1	60%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	3	0	0	1	75%
Privacy and security issues	1	0	0	0	100%
Total	19	0	2	4	80%

The tests for UC4.2 have been carried out for the most part in the Brainstorm offices given the necessary infrastructure to test the use case in real conditions. The performed tests involved making a video transmission through a commercial wired network, finding transmission problems from 100Mbps, a value much higher than the expectations raised in the project for the 5G network, but thanks to this it has been verified that even with these quality values, both, video encoding at the sender, and decoding at the client, works correctly under those conditions.

3.10.5 Next Steps

As for UC4.1, which is also developed by BRA, the next steps will implement the connection with all the enablers that the project infrastructure provides. First the implementation of MQTT communication for the service and connected clients. These features will allow the communication with the others infrastructure components and the coordination of the migration operations based on these communications.

The implementation and codification of CAM messages from the VR players (clients) and their transmission/reception to/from the V2X broker will enable the VR clients monitorization by the resources allocation and management system (PRAE) in a similar way as the automated cars. The replication of the OBUs communication employing a SW prototype will also allow the simulation in lab, of GPS tracks at the final

experimental locations and testing in this way a real positional situation but in silico conditions. This use case presents an added difficulty due to a lack of specific hardware that provides geographical location data. The use of a common laptop will need the employment of network provided location data. The comparison of the lab settings results, where location data is simulated, versus field trials results, where clients are using network-based location data, will provide interesting insights about location performances in a 5G network infrastructure.

The communication with the other involved enablers such the integration fabric (IF), will allow the reception of experiment start, experiment ID and stop experiment parameters, coming from the TWP, to synchronise all the experimental operations along all the clients and services involved. The messaging via MQTT will allow the communication with the assisted service continuity to receive the information needed by the clients to connect to their service when entering the visiting domain.

3.11 UC5.1 Connected logistics

3.11.1 Use Case Overview

3.11.1.1 Use Case Description

Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.

Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, i.e., transportation needs to be monitored continuously via remote control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity.

Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard device, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.

Both of these themes will follow the same test logic and KPIs, which focus on continuous 5G service availability and quality of service levels. During the trials these aspects will be tested in test drives with:

- service interruption e.g., for upload of cargo integrity data and cybersecurity health data;
- service capacity point of view e.g., for surveillance camera uplink feed;
- service quality.

With available test networks the aim is to test and analyse service continuity in border crossing multi-MNO cases, which is a typical requirement for international logistics and end user solutions. Finally test results will be used to analyse the overall SQL (Structured Query Language), scalability and readiness for logistics end-user services.

Figure 64: UC5.1 test set-up.

3.11.1.2 Roadmap of UC5.1 in the 5G-ROUTES Project

Testing and piloting was started on lab trials and pretesting, where devices and test setup was evaluated. Very first test was held on November 2021. During the spring 2022, these tests were continued between Vedia, Enide and VTT. In parallel, preparations for the ferry as test platform were done together with Eckerö Line and their commercial communication service provider. During the years 2022 and 2023, the project’s maritime trial strategy was changed and a new pilot site was shifted to Riga bay, for which connected logistics was pivoted. In Autumn 2023, due the changes in the project beneficiaries, the pilot site was proposed to shift back to Finland Estonia corridor and especially to the coast of Finland.

The UC 5.1 lab testing included testing in Vedia office and VTT test premises in Espoo/Finland with available test networks. Plan is to continue these tests due the changes in the pilot plans and changes in test site. New pre-testing round is planned for October to December 2023. And hence to ensure readiness for actual field tests. During the pre-tests, partners will test different setups and system combinations to ensure desired system functionalities. All these tests will be first tested in NSA networks and when SA is available testing will be repeated in 5G ROUTES test sites.

3.11.1.3 Components

- 5G SA/NSA test networks
- Satellite communication connection
- Terminals (5G radio)
- Vedia test application
- Vedia VCU onboard unit with RTK
- Backhaul antenna and receiver connected to Ericsson base station
- 5G test devices and -equipment (vehicle onboard unit)
- Video camera + IoT sensors (location and temperature)
- Enide Freight management tracking (web)app
- Finbo test ferry (tbc)
- Test vehicle

3.11.1.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 65 shows the sequence diagram of UC5.1, as it was planned during the lab trials in 2022. The architecture of the maritime solution in 5G-ROUTES is being updated in 2023, and the sequence diagram will be adapted according to the final architecture.

Figure 65: UC5.1 sequence diagram.

3.11.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

For the UC5.1 first joint lab trial was performed on 16.11.2021, where in VTT's Espoo test environment Vedia's OBU (Vehicle Computing Unit - VCU) and Enide's freight management tracking (web)app was tested together. In the relevant experiment, a test vehicle was driving the trial route and an OBU was gathering temperature, time and location data from the test drive. This data was shared to Enide via MQTT protocol. The aim is to utilise this same setup in actual field tests, where this data and connectivity is used as a sample to monitor connectivity.

During the H1 2022 Vedia has worked with mMTC test application and performed preparations for OBU 5G test network testing together with VTT. During spring 2023, it was decided to redesign the UC5.1 and mMTC was removed off from the UC. First 5G test network lab trials were done during Q2 2022 together with VTT, in VTT's test network. The aim of the verification process is to test communication and connectivity against KPIs. The lab trials aim on the other hand, is to test different functions of devices and interoperability between devices and systems. For lab trials, tests must be repeated as many times as necessary, until the devices and system work as planned. Field tests will provide data and information about the network quality, capacity and coverage, which are reflected against KPIs.

3.11.3 Lab Trial Results

During the first lab trials Vedia OBU and Enide connection was tested in Espoo Finland in November 2021. This test was successfully repeated in April 2022. Due the significant changes in the pilot plan field trial readiness needs to be reanalysed during the Q4 223.

3.11.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

Table 26: Field trial readiness for UC5.1.

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	4	0	3	0	79%
OBU related issues	4	0	5	1	65%
External servers	1	0	5	0	58%
Other end user devices	1	0	2	4	29%
UE related issues	10	0	15	5	58%
Tenant Web Portal	4	0	0	4	50%
Enabler related issues	4	0	0	4	50%
5G network related issues	0	0	2	2	25%
Network handover related issues	0	0	0	3	0%
Network related issues	0	0	2	5	14%
Privacy and security issues	0	0	1	1	25%
Total	14	0	18	15	48%

3.11.5 Next steps

In early April 2022, hardware set up and installation plan was jointly agreed with Eckerö Line. In May and June 2022, installation schedule was planned and agreed together with Eckerö. The aim was to execute installations during the summer 2022. Telia planned installations for the 700 MHz base station to the Muuga harbour in August 2022, but these plans were not realised. In September 2023, the plan for the maritime solution and testing multi-hop was modified. The aim is to first test connectivity (including multi-hop) solution in 5G SA test networks in Otaniemi, and after tests on land, proceed to perform tests on the ferry. The aim is to start tests by

testing different subsections of the ferry communication infrastructure and after successful tests to do testing for each connectivity scenario. Later on, these scenarios will be combined to test final communication setup for the ferry use case.

3.12 UC5.2 5G-Based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight

3.12.1 Use Case Overview

The scope of this use case is to provide the means of allocating the proper network resources, so that a ferry can smoothly manage passengers moving in or out of the ferry at a port and also be able to load/unload properly its cargo.

3.12.1.1 Use Case Description

The use case 5.2 focuses on the management of approaching passengers, trucks and freight in a cross-border environment. The cross-border environment is located at a place during the ferry trip between Estonia and Finland or at the Valga –Valka depending on the 5G network availability. The use case provides mechanisms for notifications on approaching passengers and freight and assignment of necessary resources in the foreign or destination network. During the field trials at the border crossing it is important to leverage on heterogeneous inputs from vehicles, transferred goods and people and to select the required slice according to some priority rules and possibly SLA arrangements. The selection of the proper slice is done since the destination network has allocated a number of slices and this use case will use the slice negotiator enabler which is going to be used for the selection of the right slice. Finally, it is important to include actions for setting-up and configuring the telecommunication network and any potential vertical aspects. In the second phase, the multimodality aspect can be tackled when unloading of freight from e.g. trucks and loading to ships can take place in addition to passengers' movement. In this phase, there can be automated checking of freight (towards zero-touch) and conducting logistics operations.

Data originating from the sensors of the OBU located in the car and from the RSUs located outside in specific places of the border exchange information with an MQTT server situated at both sides of the border to identify passengers, truck location, and other traffic characteristics. The enablers used in this use case are:

The assisted handover enabler that helps to maintain data continuity across border by pre-assigning the IP address at the foreign network. The slice negotiator enabler that selects a slice with the proper resources at the visiting network.

Updated scenario to meet the needs of the project

The update of use case 5.2 needed to focus and adjust the work on the maritime ecosystem and the work is focused on the communication between ferries and between a ferry and the harbour. This communication is based on live video streaming so that the ferry driver could have a live communication with its staff, with another ferry located in a cross border and with the harbour administration when it is needed. Data originating from the camera of the OBU located in a van in the ferry exchange information with an application server in the cloud. For this scenario it is crucial to test the interruption time at the cross border and the network capability to provide high throughput originated at the camera.

3.12.1.2 Roadmap

Roadmap of past work

Lab scenario 1: This scenario was based on the final evaluation of the use case by testing the data from the sensors of the OBU, the interaction of the OBU with the MQTT server, the continuity of the data in the visiting

network, the tenant web portal that initiates the use case and the KPIs performance during the lifecycle of the slice at the visiting network.

Roadmap, updated in 2023:

Lab trial scenario 1: In the simple case there will be video streaming of low quality between the two ferries. The data stream will be a few Mbytes and the service interruption time will be measure and evaluated.

Lab trial scenario 2: Test the high throughput from the camera. The resolution of the camera will be adjusted to accommodate cases of adjusted bit rates to detect the network capability.

The testing of the functionality of the use case application will be performed firstly at the WINGS lab with the functionality of testing the live video streaming from a server to a client, where the video camera is situated on an OBU. Then the tests will be performed in a ferry as it routes in the sea and communicates with another ferry and/or with the administration office in the harbour.

3.12.1.3 Components

A 5G local commercial network will be used for testing the functionality of the use case. The OBU which is going to be used in the vehicle will be equipped with a camera for video streaming communication between ferries and between a ferry and/or between a ferry and an administration office. The OBU is based on the Quectel chip.

A camera will be used also and attached to the OBU for the live video streaming.

3.12.1.4 Sequence Diagram

The sequence diagram for the UC5.2 is shown in the following Figure 66. This figure shows the information flow between the main components of the use case.

Figure 66: Sequence diagram for UC5.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

The functionality of the use case will be tested first in the local lab of WINGS. The use case has been updated in order to meet the requirements of the project at the maritime cross border.

Sequence diagram for the update scenario

The workflow for the updated scenario considers a camera installed in the OBU and a device (ex. H/Y with a client) that receives the video. The sequence diagram is shown in the following figure.

Figure 67: Sequence diagram for the updated UC5.2 scenario

3.12.2 Lab Trial Results

Originally the lab trials involved the testing of an **OBU** with lidar, NFC and GPS sensors that was tested in the lab in December 2021. The OBU could send MQTT messages to an MQTT broker but the opposite remains to be verified. For the **RSU** a laser array is ordered whose purpose is to monitor people’s movement. The functionality of the RSU was also tested in WINGS lab and the exchange of MQTT messages between the OBU, RSU and a MQTT broker has occurred.

The handover assisted enabler was tested in the lab.

The slice negotiator enabler was tested by using a prioritization algorithm in which historic data are used and fixed slices are allocated in the visiting network. The testing of the algorithm with assigned number of slices was tested in April 2022.

3.12.3 Field Trial Readiness verification

Table 27: Field trial readiness for UC5.2.

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
OBU related issues	0	0	1	1	100%
External servers	0	0	1	6	80%
Other end user devices	2	0	1	5	40%
UE related issues	2	0	3	12	70%
CAM services	0	0	0	6	30%
Tenant Web Portal	4	0	0	4	50%
Enabler related issues	4	0	0	4	50%
5G network related issues	0	0	0	3	0%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	0%
Network related issues	3	0	0	3	50%
Total	9	0	3	25	28%

In June 2022, the CAM service was not yet tested and the external server and the use case application were under preparation.

Updated Field Trial Readiness verification

- WebRTC to be tested for real-time video;
- Enhanced video compression options;
- Improved error handling and logging.

3.12.4 Next steps

Following the refocusing of the project, in order to put more stress on cross-border aspects, the use case has been revised for providing video streaming between ferries at a cross border and between a ferry and the maritime administration office at the harbour. The OBU with the camera is under testing at the lab of WINGS. The new use case title is “Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at a cross border”. For this scenario it is crucial to test the interruption time at the cross border and the network capability to provide high throughput originated at the camera.

For the next steps, the OBU with the video camera is under preparation and will be tested in December 2023 in WINGS lab. The use case application will be tested in March 2024 when the infrastructure in a ferry will be implemented.

3.13 UC5.3 Continuous Railway Infrastructure Monitoring with Optical Sensors

3.13.1 Use Case Overview

3.13.1.1 Use Case Description

The use case 5.3 focuses on continuous railway telemetry data acquisition pre-processing and transfer to a centralised server. The captured data is used for further analysis of any deviations from railway infrastructure normal state and decision-making for the necessity to perform a detailed check or railway infrastructure maintenance. The data will be collected using multiple sensors and cameras, including event camera and high-resolution visual camera. Hence, large amounts of data are transferred via the 5G network. The network capability, while transferring the sensor and camera data to edge-cloud computing unit and further to the cloud server, will be tested.

UC5.3 includes lab testing at the railway depot and field testing on Valga-Valka border crossing railway section. The lab tests location - Riga passenger train depot and nearby territory - is chosen because it has all necessarily railway infrastructure tracks (with various level of quality), passenger trains and locomotives and limited performance 5G coverage. These conditions will enable us to pick and test the right sensor location on the train and overall system architecture prior to further trials that will take place Limbazi-Valka common use railway infrastructure. This public railway infrastructure section will allow us to monitor sensor and network performance in close to real life conditions.

There are planned 4 lab trial scenarios, which will be performed prior to field trials:

- **Lab trial scenario 1:** Depth camera and high-resolution camera performance evaluation on railway infrastructure monitoring with local data processing and storage. Tests are performed in the passenger train depot in Riga and surrounding territory. The main objective of this test is to integrate and test sensor kit deployment/construction elements, sensor performance and edge computing node performance.
- **Lab trial scenario 2:** This scenario implies sending data from the sensors installed on the train to cloud server via mobile network, perform sensor data processing and interpretation and measure required computing resources per channel. The main objectives of the test are to validate cloud computing unit performance and measure the require computing resources.
- **Lab trial scenario 3:** The test will be performed on the common use railway infrastructure in Latvia, on regular train speed, so it will be possible to monitor sensor and network performance in close to real life conditions.
- **Lab trial scenario 4:** Final application of overall functionality. The test is aimed to check sensor data transition while crossing Latvian-Estonian boarder.

The main KPIs measured are the minimum granted throughput and end-to-end latency.

3.13.1.2 Roadmap of the Railway Infrastructure Monitoring in 5G-ROUTES Project

Railway infrastructure monitoring use case development is organised in several lab trials, field trials, and development stages. The stages are as follows:

- Lab trial #1 – Sensor and connectivity tests – one of the objectives is to identify whether passenger train onboard high-performance generator and radio station negatively impact system performance.
- Field trial #1 – Depth camera and high-resolution camera performance evaluation on common use railway infrastructure monitoring with local/edge data processing and storage. As for the first field trials the 5G SA network will not be available yet, they will be performed on the already available 5G NSA network.
- Lab trial #2 - Sensor kit improvements test in depo and 5G router performance evaluation.
- Field trial #2 – Sensor and connectivity performance evaluation using 5G SA network at a cross-border.
- Lab trials #3 - Complete trial which includes sensor data capturing, edge processing, streaming over 5G network, base station processing and streaming to data centre at the Riga passenger train depot territory.
- Field trial #3 - Final validation. Tests in the cross-border corridor.

3.13.1.3 Components

The following components are relevant for a complete execution and evaluation of UC5.3:

- Sensor kit (GNSS, temperature, IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit), High resolution camera, event camera, etc).
- 5G modem and SIM card
- Fog server
- Edge processing unit
- Cloud server
- Platform - PV test diesel train (DR2)
- 5G SA/NSA test networks
- Data processing software

3.13.1.4 Sequence Diagram

The sequence diagram for the UC5.3 is shown in Figure 68. This figure shows the information flow between the main components of the use case.

Figure 68: Sequence diagram for UC5.3.

3.13.2 Lab Trials and Verification Process

First UC5.3 lab trials took place in the Riga passenger train depot on 28.02.2022. The route of the train run during the test is depicted in Figure 69. During the test, a depth and visual camera prototype was placed in different locations inside the train driver cabin and a short ride was performed with the train covering a total distance of 1km. Furthermore, data obtained from the cameras was analysed and considered for further improvements of the prototype and for finding best location on the train (Figure 70).

Figure 69: Riga passenger train depot and the test route

3.13.3 Lab Trial Results

Figure 70 shows a snapshot of the event camera and video data obtained from the equipment installed on the train.

Figure 70: Event camera data and video data from the sensors installed on the train.

Figure 71: LMT 5G network estimated coverage in the depot area

Aim of the verification process is to test communication and connectivity against KPIs. The aim of the lab trials is to test different locations of devices and interoperability between devices and systems. The lab trials tests must be repeated as many times as necessary until the devices and system work as planned. The field tests will provide data and information about the network quality, capacity and coverage, which are reflected against KPIs.

3.13.4 Field Trial Readiness Verification

Table 28 shows the overview of trial readiness verification for use case 5.3.

The main results of the verification tests include:

- **Vehicle related issues:** the necessary permits were granted for performing first lab trials in Riga passenger depot territory and the first sensor prototype was used for the tests. However, all the system components were not integrated in the onboard sensor and computing unit prototype, so test results are considered as “no tested” for the physical component integration.
- **External servers:** the information from the sensor kit was observed on the external computing unit, and access was granted to it. Server and software will need to be further developed for the next tests.
- **Tenant Web:** transfer of data has not been tested yet.
- **5G network:** this will be tested by the partners involved in the setup of the network. The Mikrotik router will be used. The router configuration for performing tests is under development.
- **Privacy and security:** During the lab trials in the Riga passenger depot territory there is no exchange of privacy related data, as the territory is closed and no one except the personnel can access it. After the lab trials the necessary permits from local railway authority will be granted in order to perform tests on common use railway infrastructure, which includes also the reviewal from GDPR expert and accordance to EU guidelines.

Table 28: Field trial readiness for UC5.3.

Group	Pass	Fail	Partly	Not tested	Completion%
Vehicle related issues	1	0	0	2	33%
External servers	5	0	0	1	83%
UE related issues	6	0	0	3	67%
Tenant Web	4	0	0	3	57%
Enabler related issues	4	0	0	3	57%
5G network related issues	0	0	0	2	0%
Network handover related issues	3	0	0	0	100%
Network related issues	3	0	0	2	60%
Privacy and security issues	0	0	0	1	0%
Total	13	0	0	9	59%

3.13.5 Next Steps

During the refocusing of the project in Summer 2022, it was decided to discontinue work on this use case, as the infrastructure, which is planned to be deployed for the road use cases, is not covering the rail tracks in Valga-Valka.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusions

This deliverable gives an overview of the first set of lab trials and the tests for assessing the readiness for 5G NSA field trials. After the end of the lab trials, the planned 5G NSA field trials were cancelled due to refocusing of the project. During the planned field trials, 2 enablers were intended to be used: the V2X message routing servicer and the Tenant Web Portal, which were both deployed on the cloud.

Table 29 shows the readiness for 5G NSA field trials. Aspects which are still under development in September 2023 are related to the integration of the logging (i.e., automated starting and stopping of logging at experiments, allowing to harmonise the timing of the logs at different devices and automated upload of the logs at the end of the experiments) and have not yet been tested. Issues which still not be integrated further by the use cases mainly relate to logging (such as the synchronisation of the different data) and the integration with the enablers.

The overall completion for all the use cases percentage is 76% (including the discontinued use cases UC2.2, UC3.2 and UC5.2 and the refocused use cases UC5.2 and UC3.3).

Table 29. Overview of the 5G NSA field trial readiness completion for the use cases

Group	UC1.1	UC1.2	UC1.3	UC2.1	UC2.2	UC3.1	UC3.2	UC3.3	UC4.1	UC4.2	UC5.1	UC5.2	UC5.3
Vehicle related issues	94 %	100 %	100 %		89 %	100 %	100 %	100 %			79 %		33 %
OBU related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %		70 %	100 %	81 %	100 %			65 %	33 %	
Infrastructure related issues				71 %									
External servers	92 %	92 %		50 %	83 %		100 %	100 %		100 %	58 %	0 %	83 %
Other end user devices								100 %	83 %	83 %	29 %	31 %	
Subtotal: user device related issues	96 %	98 %	100 %	62 %	80 %	100 %	92 %	100 %	83 %	92 %	58 %	21 %	67 %
CAM services			100 %						100 %			0 %	
Privacy and security issues			100 %	0 %			0 %			100 %	25 %		0 %
Subtotal: Use case specific	96 %	98 %	100 %	64 %	80 %	100 %	87 %	100 %	92 %	92 %	56 %	15 %	60 %
Tenant Web Portal	81 %	81 %	71 %	50 %	50 %	75 %	50 %	88 %	71 %	63 %	50 %	50 %	57 %
V2X router				10 %		100 %		80 %					
Subtotal_ Enabler related issues	81 %	81 %	71 %	35 %	50 %	83 %	50 %	85 %	71 %	63 %	50 %	50 %	57 %
5G network related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	25 %	0 %	0 %
Network handover related issues	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %
Subtotal: Network related issues	100 %	75 %	75 %	14 %	50 %	60 %							
Total	93 %	95 %	94 %	58 %	76 %	94 %	81 %	96 %	83 %	80 %	48 %	28 %	59 %

Cross-border tests were performed for both UC3.2 and UC3.3. In UC3.3 the network change was forced through shutting down the base station, and the service disruption time was about 3 seconds. For UC3.2, 5G NSA roaming was used and the interruption time was in the order of 30 seconds. In these tests, the Mikrotik 5G router, which will be used by most of the use cases (except when specific devices such as smart phones are used).

4.2 Recommendations

The original plan included lab trials performed in specified lab trial sites, including CTTC, TTU and VTT. However, for efficient use of resources, the benefit of performing lab trials at dedicated sites should be higher than the

additional effort needed for deploying the tests at the lab sites. Especially for tests involving vehicles this is challenging: the interfaces in vehicles to both actuators, sensors and the control system are not standardised, and hence very challenging to transfer to vehicles from other developers. During the first set of lab trial sets the tests were therefore performed in locations near the developers. During the second test of lab trials, the use cases will be tested remotely with the CAM Services Platform, which is installed in the lab of CTTC.

4.3 Next Steps

This deliverable reports on the lab trials, which are performed in preparation of the first set of field trials, which were planned to be performed in the second half of 2022. However, due to refocusing of the project, the 5G NSA trials were cancelled, as well as several of the use cases.

The first set of lab trials is hence followed by a second set of lab trials, where the use cases are integrated with the CAM Services Platform of the 5G-ROUTES project. This includes both integration of CAM services, used by the use cases, in the CAM Services Platform and integration of both the CAM services and the UEs with the enablers of the CAM Services Platform. An example of the integration and testing of the use case can be found in Annex 2.

5 References

- [1] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.1 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0, https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/D1.1_Use-Cases-scenarios-specs-target-KPIs-for-5G-for-CAM-v1.0_Submitted.pdf
- [2] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D1.9 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0
- [3] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.3 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0, https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/D1.3_Report-on-5G-ROUTES-CAM-deployment-plan-and-longer-term-deployment-strategies-v1.0_Submitted.pdf
- [4] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM, https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Attachment_3.1.pdf
- [5] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0, https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/5G-ROUTES-D1.7-TestFramework_v1.0_201130_VTT-FINAL.pdf
- [6] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D1.12 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0
- [7] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.1 AI Assisted Cross-Domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM Services
- [8] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.3 AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services v1.0
- [9] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.5 AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X v1.0
- [10] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.7 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1
- [11] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM 1.0, https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/5G-ROUTES_D2.9-Report-on-integration-and-testing-of-technological-enablers-v1.0.pdf
- [12] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.3 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0
- [13] Novickis, Rihards, Aleksandrs Levinskis, Vitalijs Fescenko, Roberts Kadikis, Kaspars Ozols, Anna Ryabokon, Rupert Schorn et al. "Development and Experimental Validation of High Performance Embedded Intelligence and Fail-Operational Urban Surround Perception Solutions of the PRYSTINE Project." *Applied Sciences* 12, no. 1 (2021): 168.
- [14] Deming, W. Edwards (1986). *Out of the crisis*. Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- [15] 5G-MOBIX (2021) D3.6 Report on field trial readiness verifications
- [16] Kubernetes(2022) Kubernetes Documentation <https://kubernetes.io/docs/home/>
- [17] C-ROADS Platform (2021) C-ITS IP Based Interface Profile, version 2.0
- [18] J. Schwartz (2018), Bing Maps Tile System, <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/bingmaps/articles/bing-maps-tile-system>
- [19] CARLA (2022), Open-source simulator for autonomous driving research, <https://carla.org/>
- [20] Kaitotek (2022) Qosium, <https://www.kaitotek.com/qosium>
- [21] Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi (2018), YOLOv3: An Incremental Improvement
- [22] Topi Miekka (2021), 3D Object Detection Using LIDAR Point Clouds and 2D Image Object Detection, Master Thesis, Tampere University, 5/2021, <https://trepo.tuni.fi/handle/10024/132285>
- [23] 5G-SAFE-PLUS (2020) 5G Enabled Road Safety Services, <https://5gsafeplus.fmi.fi/>
- [24] Mikrotik, Chateau 5 G, https://mikrotik.com/product/chateau_5g
- [25] Netgear Nighthawk M5 5G WiFi 6 Mobile Router Unlocked, <https://www.netgear.com/home/mobile-wifi/hotspots/mr5200/>
- [26] Huawei, Huawei 5G CPE Pro 2, <https://consumer.huawei.com/en/routers/5g-cpe-pro-2/>
- [27] Goodmill Systems, Goodmill Systems w24h-I Managed Multichannel Router, https://goodmillsystems.com/application/files/7316/7709/1753/Goodmill_w24h-I_Datasheet_2023_A4_4s.pdf

[28]U-Blox GPS, <https://www.u-blox.com/en/positioning-chips-and-modules>

[29]U-Center GNSS Evaluation Software, <https://www.u-blox.com/en/product/u-center>

[30]ETSI TS 138 331-V16.13.0 (2023) 5G; NR; Radio Resource Control (RRC); Protocol specification (3GPP TS 38.331 version 16.13.0 Release 16)

6 Annex 1: Checklists for Field Trial Readiness Verification

6.1 UC1.1 Dynamic Vehicles Platooning

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI CAVs are owned and maintained by EDI and are available for tests at any given time.
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	EDI	Riga	Pass	Vehicle 1: most components (DbW, sensors, power setup, preliminary computing platform) are deployed. Vehicle 2: DbW, power setup and preliminary computing platform available, sensor setup in progress (but trial 1 will only require communication + power setup).
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	EDI	Riga	Pass	For both vehicles, data transmission and reception has been tested and demonstrated.
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Partly	Tests have been made with virtual data and models, as well as simulations using CARLA, and tests with the real vehicles in a full control loop. Radar SW integration in progress.
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	EDI	Riga	Pass	Integration tests (CAN in the loop, MQTT communication) have been performed. Sensors relevant for trial 1 are integrated and provide correct data. Control loop capable of working with sensor inputs.
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	EDI	Riga	Pass	MQTT loopback and CAN tests were done for transmitting OBD data. Sensor data available for processing.
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	EDI	Riga	Pass	CAM packet exchange was tested.
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control	EDI	Riga	Pass	DbW system was deployed, driver fallback successfully tested.
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Relevant driving data (vehicle kinematics, control loop performance) has been recorded in rosbag and other formats.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	Sensor data transmission and communication with second vehicle has been tested.
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	LMT	Riga	Pass	Mikrotik 5G modem has been tested by LMT.
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	EDI	Riga	Pass	Standard encoding was agreed between partners.
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	EDI	Riga	Pass	OBU can send and receive kinematics data between vehicles and handle sensor data.
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	EDI	Riga	Pass	NDT matching for localization in lidar map was tested. Initial position estimation and localization with improved GNSS also tested.
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	EDI	Riga	Pass	GNSS-based synchronization tested between two OBUs, using PPS signals.
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	TELIA, LMT	Riga	Pass	2 SIM cards received from LMT
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Candump and rosbag recordings of sensor and communication data is available.
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server deployed and tested.
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access			Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server available and only used by EDI. VTT-owned MQTT server available for EDI.
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	ROS/MQTT bridge has been tested.
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications			Pass	Sensor, vehicle control, CAM messages and communication with V2X broker tested.
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server			Partly	Using absolute timestamp of ROS generated messages, as well V2X broker statistics.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Data relating to V2V reliability and latency has been recorded.
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal			Partly	Sample test trials attempted via TWP
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			Partly	Sample test trials attempted via TWP
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Pass	Data format was discussed among partners
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other			Partly	CAMs with synchronized timestamps have been recorded. Additions to existing CAMs are still needed to include non-standard values like vehicle-to-vehicle distance data.
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	LMT, TELIA		Pass	The whole area of Bikernieki is covered
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2			Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...			Not relevant	Planned tests: MQTTS integration (trial #2 or later)

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (GDPR, C-ITS security policy)			Not relevant	there are no privacy-related issues, and any usage of optical sensors like cameras is only meant to yield relevant metadata like lane markings

6.2 UC1.2 Cooperative Lane Change

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI CAVs are owned and maintained by EDI and are available for tests at any given time.
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	EDI	Riga	Pass	Vehicle 1: most components (DbW, sensors, power setup, preliminary computing platform) are deployed. Vehicle 2: DbW, power setup and preliminary computing platform available, sensor setup in progress (but trial 1 will only require communication + power setup).
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	EDI	Riga	Pass	For both vehicles, data transmission and reception has been tested and demonstrated.
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	Lane-following tests with lane-change have been performed in Bikernieki.
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	EDI	Riga	Pass	Integration tests (CAN in the loop, MQTT communication) have been performed. Sensors relevant for trial 1 are integrated and provide correct data.
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	EDI	Riga	Pass	MQTT loopback and CAN tests were done for transmitting OBD data. Sensor data available for processing.
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	EDI	Riga	Pass	CAM packet exchange was tested.
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control	EDI	Riga	Pass	DbW system was deployed, driver fallback successfully tested.
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Relevant driving data (vehicle kinematics, lidar measurements) has been recorded in rosbag and other formats.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	Sensor data transmission and communication with second vehicle has been tested.
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	LMT	Riga	Pass	Mikrotik 5G modem has been tested by LMT.
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	EDI	Riga	Pass	Standard encoding was agreed between partners.
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	EDI	Riga	Pass	OBU can send and receive kinematics data between vehicles and handle sensor data.
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	EDI	Riga	Pass	NDT matching for localization in lidar map was tested. Initial position estimation and localization with improved GNSS also tested.
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	EDI	Riga	Pass	GNSS-based synchronization tested between two OBUs, using PPS signals.
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	TELIA, LMT	Riga	Pass	2 SIM cards received from LMT
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Candump and rosbag recordings of sensor and communication data is available, including information relevant for lane following.
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server deployed and tested.
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access			Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server available and only used by EDI. VTT-owned MQTT server available for EDI.
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	ROS/MQTT bridge has been tested.
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications			Pass	Sensor, vehicle control, CAM messages and communication with V2X broker tested.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server			Partly	Using absolute timestamp of ROS generated messages, as well MQTT broker statistics.
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Data relating to V2V reliability and latency has been recorded.
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal			Partly	Sample test trials attempted via TWP
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			Partly	Sample test trials attempted via TWP
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Pass	Data format were was discussed among partners
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other			Partly	CAMs with synchronized timestamps have been recorded. Additions to existing CAMs are still needed to include non-standard values like vehicle-to-vehicle distance data.
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	LMT, TELIA		Pass	The whole area of Bikernieki is covered
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...			Not relevant	Planned tests: MQTTS integration (trial #2 or later)
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (GDPR, C-ITS security policy)			Not relevant	there are no privacy-related issues, and any usage of optical sensors like cameras is only meant to yield relevant metadata like lane markings

6.3 UC1.3 See-Through View for Safe Automated Overtaking

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	The equipment can be placed in a vehicle from EDI, LMT or in a rental vehicle.
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	VTT	Tampere	Pass	
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control	VTT	Otaniemi, Tampere	Pass	
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	. The vehicle data will be logged together with the OBU data.
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	VTT	Otaniemi, Tampere	Pass	OBU1 consist of laptop, modem, camera and GNSS. OBU2 consist of laptop, modem and GNSS. OBUs have been used in other projects. Integration with camera is tested in Otaniemi

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	The video exchange has been tested in laboratory conditions and in commercial 5G network. Handover has not been able to be tested in Finland
V14	The OBUs can manage and run 3 rd party the required applications	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Video encoding and decoding has been tested
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	LMT	Riga	Pass	The Mikrotik modem provided by LMT will be used. For tests in Finland, other modems including Huawei CPE and Netgear Nighthawk have been used.
V16	The OBUs have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform			Not relevant	The 5G-ROUTES platform is not yet operational
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)			Not relevant	GNSS sufficient at this stage
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	VTT	Otaniemi, Tampere	Pass	The synchronization uses the NTP software Chrony
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA		Pass	MNOs are committed to deliver the SIMs
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests			Pass	
CAM-services related issues					
C1	The CAM-services can be deployed in the field trial site	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Video proxy will be deployed on cloud for the NSA tests.
C2	The CAM-services can connect to all relevant end-user devices, 5G-ROUTES enablers and external servers	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	connection between the OBU and the proxy has been tested in lab and during travel tests
C3	The CAM services have access to all required data			Not relevant	Proxy does not need any data from vehicle
C4	The CAM services behave as expected and have been validated	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Tested in vehicles and in lab
C6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VTT	Otaniemi	Not relevant	No data are stored at the CAM service. Qosium data logged at the UE.
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	VTT	Otaniemi	Not relevant	Data is produced using the Qosium tool.
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	VTT	Otaniemi	Pass	tested in Qosium
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	The whole area of Bikernieki is covered.
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised			Not relevant	No data are logged at the network side
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...			not relevant	no ETSI certificates in use. Security for the MQTT broker is through password and restricted IP address.
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)			Pass	A sticker will be attached to the vehicle related to the use of camera by the vehicle. The streamed video will not be recorded.

6.4 UC2.1 Real-Time Traffic Information and Cooperative Intersection Collision Control

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Infrastructure related issues					
I1	The availability of the infrastructure sensors is assured	SWARCO	Valka/Valga cities	Pass	Road infrastructure has been installed
I2	The infrastructure sensors connect and have access to the 5G network	SWARCO		Pass	
I4	The infrastructure sensors are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	SWARCO		Partly	
I5	Synchronisation measures are used for the infrastructure	SWARCO		Not tested	
I6	Applications at the infrastructure (edge) are working correctly and have real-time access to all required data	SWARCO		Partly	Road users' detection and traffic data collection achieved
I7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA		Pass	LMT and TELIA delivered the SIMs
I8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	SWARCO		Pass	
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	SWARCO		Pass	
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	SWARCO		Not tested	
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	SWARCO		Partly	Applications continue being tested
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	SWARCO		Partly	Sensor, road infrastructure, CAM messages
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	SWARCO		Not tested	
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	SWARCO		Pass	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other			Not tested	
V2X broker					
EV1	The end-user applications can connect to the V2X broker			Partly	
EV2	The end-user applications publish messages according to the agreed protocol			Not tested	
EV3	The end-user applications receive the messages to which they have subscribed			Not tested	
EV4	The algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages work as expected			Not tested	
EV5	Metrics (can be logged) and can be downloaded			Not tested	
5G network related issues					
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure			Pass	
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks			Pass	The coverage in Valga-Valka has been confirmed by LMT and Telia
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised			Not relevant	No data are logged at the network side

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g., GDPR)	SWARCO		Pass	GDPR compliant

6.5 UC2.2 Traffic Jam Chauffeur

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI CAVs are owned and maintained by EDI and are available for tests at any given time.
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	EDI	Riga	Pass	Vehicle 1: most components (DbW, sensors, power setup, preliminary computing platform) are deployed. Vehicle 2: DbW, power setup and preliminary computing platform available, sensor setup in progress (but trial 1 will only require communication + power setup).
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	EDI	Riga	Pass	For both vehicles, data transmission and reception has been tested and demonstrated.
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Partly	Virtual tests for lane-following have been done. Final integration of relevant algorithms in the vehicle's system in progress.
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	EDI	Riga	Pass	Integration tests (CAN in the loop, MQTT communication) have been performed. Sensors relevant for trial 1 are integrated and provide correct data.
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	EDI	Riga	Partly	MQTT loopback and CAN tests were done for transmitting OBD data. Sensor data available for processing. Traffic-related message to be defined.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	EDI	Riga	Pass	CAM packet exchange was tested.
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control	EDI	Riga	Pass	DbW system was deployed, driver fallback successfully tested.
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Relevant driving data (vehicle kinematics, lidar measurements) has been recorded in rosbag and other formats.
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	EDI	Riga	Pass	Trial 1 OBU-setup available for both vehicles.
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	Sensor data transmission and communication with second vehicle has been tested.
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	LMT	Riga	Pass	Mikrotik 5G modem has been tested by LMT.
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	EDI	Riga	Partly	Standard encoding was agreed between partners.
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	EDI	Riga	Partly	OBU can send and receive kinematics data between vehicles and handle sensor data. Traffic-related message in development.
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	EDI	Riga	Partly	NDT matching was tested. Sensor fusion with GNSS data not yet tested.
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	EDI	Riga	Not tested	NTP is considered as the synchronization protocol. GNSS synchronization is also considered as a option.
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA	Riga	Pass	MNOs are committed to provide the SIM cards
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Partly	Candump and rosbag recordings of sensor and communication data is available. Full recording of a UC2.2-specific scenario to be made.
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	EDI	Riga	Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server deployed and tested.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access			Pass	EDI-owned MQTT server available and only used by EDI. VTT-owned MQTT server available for EDI.
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	EDI	Riga	Pass	ROS/MQTT bridge has been tested.
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications			Partly	Sensor, vehicle control, CAM messages tested.
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server			Partly	Using absolute timestamp of ROS generated messages, as well MQTT broker statistics.
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	EDI	Riga	Pass	Data relating to V2V reliability and latency has been recorded.
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Not tested	Data format was discussed among partners
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other			Not tested	Data with associated timestamps were recorded, synchronisation was not yet tested.
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	LMT, TELIA		Pass	The whole area of Bikernieki is covered

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...			Not relevant	Planned tests: MQTTS integration (trial #2 or later)

6.6 UC3.1 Sensor Info Sharing for Cooperative Situation Awareness

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	VTT	Tampere	Pass	The equipment can be placed in a vehicle from EDI, LMT or in a rental vehicle.
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	VTT	Tampere	Pass	The box, containing LIDAR, camera and computing equipment, can be installed on top of a vehicle from LMT, EDI or rental vehicle with suitable fixtures.
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	VTT	Tampere	Pass	The sensor equipment sends the sensor information to the computing equipment
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	VTT	Tampere	Pass	The detection software has been validated in a static prototype.
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	VTT	Tampere	Not relevant	No specific vehicle applications during the first trials
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	VTT	Tampere	Pass	dynamic data needed for logging and CPM, is included in the tests
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	VTT, VEDECOM, SWARCO, CERTH		Pass	CPM TR103562 v2.1.1.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Logging has been developed, according to the uniform format. Data has been collected during tests in Oulu.
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	VTT	Tampere	Pass	OBU1 consist of laptop, modem, sensor box and GNSS. OBU2 consist of laptop, modem and GNSS. OBUs have been used in other projects.
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	VTT	Tampere	Pass	CPM data transmission has been tested
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	LMT	Riga	Not relevant	Video encoding and decoding has been tested
V16	The OBUs have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform			Pass	The Mikrotik modem provided by LMT will be used. For tests in Finland, other modems such as Huawei CPE and Netgear Nighthawk are used.
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	VTT, VEDECOM, SWARCO, CERTH		Not relevant	The 5G-ROUTES platform is not yet operational
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Messages have been exchanged offline, and can be decoded
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Tests have been performed with local broker. Geonetworking is not implemented in the first version.
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	VTT	Tampere	Pass	RTK is supported, and availability of RTK at test site has been confirmed
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA/		Pass	Chrony
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VTT	Tampere	Pass	LMT and TELIA are committed to provide the SIMs
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb using test data
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Tested in the TenantWeb using test data
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Logging according to the format agreed and described in D2.7
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Tested by comparing the different data files with each other
V2X broker					
EV1	The end-user applications can connect to the V2X broker	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Connection to broker in Oulu is working
EV2	The end-user applications publish messages according to the agreed protocol	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Messages comply with the MQTT specifications.
EV3	The end-user applications receive the messages to which they have subscribed	VTT	Tampere	Pass	All messages will be subscribed in trial phase
EV4	The algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages work as expected	VTT	Tampere	Not relevant	Geolocation and filtering will not be used for the first set of trials
EV5	Metrics (can be logged) and can be downloaded	VTT	Tampere	Pass	Logging has been implemented at the V2X broker
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Network in Bikernieki is covered, not tested yet for Valga-Valka
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised			Not relevant	
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...			not relevant	no ETSI certificates in use. Security for the MQTT broker is through password and restricted IP address.
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)			not relevant	Only use of research vehicles. For the detection, only metadata will be transmitted, not raw sensor data.

6.7 UC3.2 Connected Maintenance

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Description
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	TTU	NSA trials	Partly	
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	TTU	NSA trials	Partly	
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	TTU	NSA trials	Partly	
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	MQTT with SmartREST payload is used to send messages to the cloud.
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	TTU	NSA trials	pass	All measured data is uploaded to the cloud and are accessible from there for postprocess and/or download
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	TTU	NSA trials	partly	TTU has his own OBU built on Raspberry Pi platform, at the moment two OBUs are ready. Some software updates are in progress.
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	OBU is placed on passenger seat or close to vehicle windscreen, OBU is fixed with double sided tapes.
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	TTU	NSA trials	partly	As some software updates are in progress these need to be validated after they are ready. Work in progress.
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	TTU	NSA trials	pass	OBU connectivity tests performed in TTU Campus.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Description
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	OBU uses MQTT with SmartREST payload, the connectivity and message transmit/receive is tested with Cumulocity Cloud service.
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	TTU	NSA trials	partly	Currently only GNSS positioning is tested and supported.
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	TTU	NSA trials	Not relevant	In this UC no special synchronisation measures are used: only round trip time will be evaluated.
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	TTU	NSA trials	pass	On tests Telia SIM cards have been used
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	TTU	NSA trials	pass	On tests all data is sent to the cloud server.
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	TTU	NSA trials	pass	Telia Cumulocity Cloud is installed at TTU Cloud server, the service is tested and available.
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	TTU	NSA trials	pass	Telia Cumulocity Cloud is accessible from internet and also from mobile networks, Access is granted based on device registration.
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	TTU	NSA trials	pass	
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	TTU	NSA trials	pass	Messages with Cumulocity Cloud are using MQTT and Smart REST payload. REST templates are created and defined for device during device registration.
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	TTU	NSA trials	Not relevant	In this UC no special synchronisation measures are used: only round trip time will be evaluated.
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	TTU	NSA trials	pass	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Not tested	Not yet available

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Description
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web using test data
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web using test data
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	TTU	NSA trials	Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	TTU	NSA trials	Not tested	
5G network related issues					
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure	TTU	NSA trials	pass	5G Router will be used, connectivity tests done in Telia NSA network
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	TTU	NSA trials	pass	5G Router will be used, connectivity tests done in Telia NSA network
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised	TTU	NSA trials	pass	5G Router will be used, connectivity tests done in Telia NSA network
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Tested during Demo event in Riga, Test started in Telia network and HO was made over to LMT network
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Tested during Demo event in Riga, OBU has been tested both with Telia and LMT sim cards, connections were established with both networks, Telia sim card connection to LMT network was reached when roaming was allowed. Cloud connections test both with dynamic and static IP addresses (different APNs were used).
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	Tested during Demo event in Riga, Test started in Telia network and HO was made over to LMT network
N8	All relevant information is exchanged when moving between networks	TTU	NSA trials	Pass	After the HO data connection to the cloud was restored and data upload restarted

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Description
Privacy and security issues					
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)	TTU	NSA trials	Not tested	

6.8 UC3.3 VRU Collision Avoidance

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	One Vehicle ready for the tests
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	OBU is integrated into the vehicle
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	CAM generated from the OBU
V4	The vehicle applications, including the automated driving applications, behave as expected and have been validated	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Test that an alert is send when receiving notification of VRU presence
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Test application is installed with C-ITS stack
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Access to C-ITS message OK and vehicle position and time OK
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	ETSI CAM / CPM are used
V8	The vehicle has safety measures in place to allow the driver to take control	VEDECOM	Versailles	Not relevant	Vehicle not used in automated mode
V9	Permits: all necessary permits for performing the tests, including driving on public roads, have been received	VEDECOM	Versailles	Not relevant	Vehicle not used in automated mode
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Logs obtained from the application in the vehicle
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	One OBU ready

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	One OBU installed in a vehicle
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	C-ITS Stack has been validated and can interact with MQTT broker
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Tested with 5G Commercial network
V16	The OBUs have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform	VEDECOM	Versailles	Not relevant	Not tested for this iteration
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	ETSI CAM is used
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	ETSI CAM can be receive from MQTT broker
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Ok with an inertial navigation unit of the vehicle
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Synchronisation done with NTP server
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA	Riga	Pass	MNOs are committed to deliver the SIMs
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Logs can be captured at network and access layers
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	MQTT broker installed in VEDECOM data centre
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Connection to VTT server OK with need to have fixed IP
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	MQTT broker installed in VEDECOM data centre
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Topics for exchanging CAM have been agreed

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	VEDECOM	Versailles	Pass	Synchronisation done with NTP server
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	VEDECOM	Versailles	Not relevant	No data logged on external servers
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRUs, smartphones)					
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	VRU prototype device is available by CERTH
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	5G network connection was initially tested with Greek commercial public network. Also tested with commercial network in Satory and with LMT network
D3	The end-user devices have live connection to 5G-ROUTES platform	CERTH	Versailles	Not relevant	Not tested for this iteration
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	The first version of the VRU device algorithms for triggering VRU warnings has been validated in the outdoor test session
D5	The end-user devices are capable to transmit the relevant (C-ITS) messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	ETSI CAM messages are transmitted by the VRU device
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	Synchronization is done with Chrony locked on device's GNSS time and pps signal
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA	Bikernieki	Pass	MNOs are committed to deliver the SIMs
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	CERTH	Versailles	Pass	Logs are captured and stored at application layer
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM		Pass	
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM / CERTH		Not Tested	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM		Pass	
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM		Pass	
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	Data can be logged with common formats. Latency and reliability KPIs could be calculated.
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	
V2X broker					
EV1	The end-user applications can connect to the V2X broker	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	MQTT broker can be accessed
EV2	The end-user applications publish messages according to the agreed protocol	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	Topics for publish CAM have been agreed
EV3	The end-user applications receive the messages to which they have subscribed	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	Application can successfully subscribe to the broker
EV4	The algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages work as expected	VEDECOM / CERTH		Pass	No filtering done at this iteration
EV5	Metrics (can be logged) and can be downloaded			Not Tested	
5G network related issues					
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure	VEDECOM / CERTH	Bikernieki	Pass	
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	VEDECOM / CERTH	Bikernieki	Pass	
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised	VEDECOM / CERTH	Bikernieki	Pass	Data logging done on application side and use synchronisation between UEs
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.

6.9 UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-user Gaming on the Go

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRUs, smartphones)					
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available	Brainstorm		Pass	5G Android smartphones for testing will be provided by VEDIA
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network	Brainstorm		Partly	To be determined on site
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected	Brainstorm		Partly	Tested on an Android smartphone, but not yet on final models.
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices	Brainstorm		Pass	Each client measures delta times based on its own reference clock.
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, Telia		Pass	SIM Cards will be provided by MNOs for the trials.
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Brainstorm		Pass	
CAM-services related issues					
C1	The CAM-services can be deployed in the trial-site	Brainstorm		Pass	Right now, the game server is implemented as an external server, placed at Brainstorm offices. Moving it and other possible servers to Amazon Cloud will be tried for first trials.
C2	The CAM-services can connect to all relevant end-user devices, 5G-ROUTES enablers and external servers	Brainstorm		Pass	Local tests and commercial 4G network tests already done
C3	The CAM services have access to all required data	Brainstorm		Pass	Servers tested both at CTTC premises and also at Brainstorm offices with success.
C4	The CAM services behave as expected and have been validated	Brainstorm		Pass	The communication is done through UDP in a proprietary message format for communicate clients and server.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
C5	The CAM services are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	Brainstorm		Pass	Each client measures delta times based on its own reference clock.
C6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Brainstorm		Pass	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Not tested	Will be tested when Tenant Web is ready.
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Not relevant	Data logging will be upload at the end of each game session.
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	Brainstorm		Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	Brainstorm		Pass	Timestamps are measured on clients with GPS accuracy
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	Brainstorm		Not tested	To be tested on site
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Privacy and security issues					
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)			Not relevant	No personal data is transmitting during this use case

6.10 UC4.2 3D Real-time Virtual Collaboration on the Move

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	Brainstorm		Pass	Right now, the external server is placed at Brainstorm offices. Moving it and other possible servers to Amazon Cloud will be tried for first field trials.
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	Brainstorm		Pass	Local tests and commercial 4G network tests already done
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	Brainstorm		Pass	Servers tested both at CTTC premises and also at Brainstorm offices with success.
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	Brainstorm		Pass	The communication is done through UDP in a proprietary message format for communicate clients and server.
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	Brainstorm		Pass	Each client measures delta times based on its own reference clock.
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Brainstorm		Pass	
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRUs, smartphones)					
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available	Brainstorm		Pass	5G Android smartphones for testing will be provided by VEDIA
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network	Brainstorm		Partly	To be determined on site
D3	The end-user devices have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform	Brainstorm		Not relevant	5G-ROUTES platform not used during first set of trials
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected	Brainstorm		Partly	Tested on an Android smartphone, but not yet on final models.

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices	Brainstorm		Pass	Each client measures delta times based on its own reference clock.
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA		Pass	MNOs are committed to provide the SIMs
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Brainstorm		Pass	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	Brainstorm		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	Brainstorm		Pass	Timestamps are measured on clients with GPS accuracy
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks			Not tested	To be tested on site
Network handover related issues					
N5	MNO1 can manage the connectivity handover procedures with MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	All relevant information is exchanged when moving between networks			Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UC can roam between MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)			Pass	Not a technical question because the presenter will sign the standard documents used on broadcasted TV programs.

6.11 UC5.1 Goods Tracking Visibility in Multimodal Cross-Border Logistics

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V1	All CAVs are ready and available for the field trials	Vedia	Finland	Pass	
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	Vedia	Finland	Pass	
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	Vedia, Enide	Finland	Pass	
V5	The vehicle applications are correctly installed	Vedia, Enide	Finland	Partly	
V6	The vehicle application has access to all required data in real time (e.g. vehicle data, sensor data) from other components.	Vedia, Enide	Finland	Partly	
V7	Messages and data content and encoding have been agreed between partners.	Vedia, Enide	Finland	Pass	
V10	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Vedia, Enide	Finland	Partly	
OBU related issues					
V11	All OBUs are ready and available for the field trials	Vedia	Finland	Pass	
V12	The OBUs are correctly installed in the CAV/CV	Vedia	Finland	Pass	
V13	The applications in the OBU behave as expected and are validated	Vedia		Partly	
V15	The OBUs connect and have access to the 5G network	Vedia		Pass	
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	Vedia		Partly	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
V19	The OBUs allow for improved positioning (compared to GNSS positioning)	Vedia		Partly	
V20	Synchronisation measures are used for the OBU	Vedia		Partly	
V21	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	TELIA		Pass	TELIA is committed to provide the SIMs
V22	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Vedia, Telia, Ericsson, TTU, Airbus		Partly	
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	Vedia, Enide		Pass	
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	Vedia, Enide		Partly	
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	Vedia, Enide		Partly	
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	Vedia, Enide		Partly	
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	Vedia, Enide		Partly	
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Vedia, Enide, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Partly	
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRUs, smartphones)					
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available	Vedia		Partly	
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network	Vedia		Not tested	
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected	Vedia		Not tested	
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices	Vedia		Partly	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	TELIA		Pass	TELIA is committed to provide the SIMs
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	Vedia		Not tested	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, EBOS		Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, EBOS		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	Vedia, EBOS		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	
5G network related issues					
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Partly	
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU, Enide		Not relevant	No data are logged at the network side
Network handover related issues					
N5	MNO1 can manage the connectivity handover procedures with MNO2	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	
N6	All relevant information is exchanged when moving between networks	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	
N7	The UE can roam between MNO1 and MNO2	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU		Not tested	
Privacy and security issues					
P1	All involved partners can exchange messages using the agreed security protocols TLS, ETSI ITS...	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU, Enide	n	Partly	
P2	All partners have agreed on the processes for exchanging certificates and have access to the agreed certificates.	Vedia, Telia, Aribus, Ericsson, TTU, Enide		Not tested	

6.12 UC5.2 5G-Based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
OBU related issues					
V17	The OBUs are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	WINGS		Partly	
V18	The OBU receives all relevant messages (algorithms for geolocation and filtering of messages are working)	WINGS		Partly	
External servers					

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	WINGS		Not tested	
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	WINGS		Not tested	
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	WINGS		Not tested	
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	WINGS		Not tested	
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	WINGS		Not tested	
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	WINGS		Not tested	
Other end-user devices (e.g. VRUs, smartphones)					
D1	Other end-user devices, which are needed for the user story, are available	WINGS		Pass	
D2	End-user devices are connected to the network	WINGS		Not tested	
D3	The end-user devices have live connection to the 5G-ROUTES platform	WINGS		Not tested	
D4	The application algorithms on the end-user device are installed correctly and work as expected	WINGS		Not tested	
D5	The end-user devices are capable to transmit the relevant (C-ITS) messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	WINGS		Partly	
D6	Synchronisation measures are used for the end-user devices	WINGS		Not tested	
D7	SIM cards are available for the field trials, and attach to the 5G network	LMT, TELIA		Pass	MNOs are committed to provide the SIMs
D8	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	WINGS		Not tested	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
CAM-services related issues					
C1	The CAM-services can be deployed in the field trial site	WINGS		Not tested	
C2	The CAM-services can connect to all relevant end-user devices, 5G-ROUTES enablers and external servers	WINGS		Not tested	
C3	The CAM services have access to all required data	WINGS		Not tested	
C4	The CAM services behave as expected and have been validated	WINGS		Not tested	
C5	The CAM services are capable to transmit and receive the relevant messages according to the relevant standard and encoding	WINGS		Not tested	
C6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	WINGS		Not tested	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped, and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal	WINGS		Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats	WINGS		Not tested	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	WINGS		Not tested	

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
5G network related issues					
N1	All partners have access to the needed interfaces and infrastructure	WINGS		Not tested	
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	WINGS		Not tested	
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised	WINGS		Not relevant	No data are logged at the network side
Network handover related issues					
N5	MNO1 can manage the connectivity handover procedures with MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N6	All relevant information is exchanged when moving between networks	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam between MNO1 and MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.

6.13 UC5.3 Continuous Railway Infrastructure Monitoring with Optical Sensors

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
Vehicle related issues					
V2	The physical components are integrated and operate correctly	PV		Not tested	
V3	The physical components, integrated in the vehicle, send the correct information	PV		Not tested	
V9	Permits: all necessary permits for performing the tests, including driving on public roads, have been received	PV		Pass	In order to perform tests on common use railway infrastructure, a permit from local railway infrastructure managing authority has to be granted
External servers					
S1	External servers and software, which are needed for the user story, are available	PV		Pass	Currently servers for prototype testing are used. It is planned to purchase a dedicated server for the use case needs.
S2	External servers are connected to the network and accessible by all partners needing access	PV		Pass	Only PV currently needs access to the server

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
S3	The applications on the external servers have been installed correctly and behave as expected and have been validated	PV		Pass	Server for prototype testing is currently running the needed applications
S4	Messages with the servers can be exchanged according to the relevant specifications	PV		Pass	Server for prototype testing is currently running the needed applications
S5	Synchronisation measures are used for the server	PV		Not tested	Synchronisation not implemented yet
S6	All required data are logged during the tests, and can be retrieved after the tests	PV		Pass	
Enabler related issues					
Tenant Web Portal					
ET1	The use case can be configured in the Tenant Web Portal	PV		Pass	Use case and scenario data can be entered in the Tenant Web
ET2	Data logging at the different UEs and CAM services can be started from the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET3	Data logging can be stopped and data uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			Not tested	Not yet available
ET4	Stored data can be retrieved from the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Stored data can be viewed in the Tenant Web
ET5	KPIs can be entered into the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET6	KPIs can be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal			Pass	Tested in the Tenant Web
ET7	Data is logged according to agreed formats			Not relevant	
ET8	Timestamps for all logged data are consistent with each other	PV		Not tested	
5G network related issues					
N2	The complete test area is covered by the 5G-networks	PV		Not tested	Not tested yet
N3	All applications and data logging are synchronised	PV		Not tested	Not tested yet
Network handover related issues					
N5	The MNOs can manage the connectivity handover procedures	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs

ID	Issue	Partner	Location	Result	Explanation
N6	The UE can connect to both MNO1 and MNO2			Pass	Has been tested by the MNOs
N7	The UE can roam from MNO1 to MNO2	Telia, LMT	Bikernieki	Pass	Has been tested, handover using ping test takes about 10 seconds.
Privacy and security issues					
P3	Exchange of privacy related data, including vehicle related information and video, is in line with EU guidelines (e.g. GDPR)	PV		Not tested	Will be checked with GDPR expert, when running tests on common use railway infrastructure

7 Annex 2: Integration of use cases with the CAM Services Platform

The main part of the report describes the lab trials which were performed in Spring 2022, in preparation of 5G NSA field trials. In these tests, the only enablers which were used were the V2X message routing service and the Tenant Web Portal, which were deployed at the cloud.

In Autumn 2022 and Spring 2023, the CAM Services Platform was further developed, and the basic technological enablers were deployed and initially tested in an experimental environment at CTTC laboratory. These enablers are the Integration Fabric, the CAM Repository, the V2X Router, and the Assisted Service Continuity. This Annex will briefly describe, for a single example use case, namely UC1.3 (low-latency video streaming), the integration of its virtualized CAM service backend with the available enablers.

The different enablers of the CAM Services Platform are described in more detail in D2.1 [7] and D2.9 [11].

7.1 Interaction between UE, CAM service and CAM Services Platform

The envisaged interaction between the virtualized video proxy CAM Service and the CAM Services Platform is as follows:

- The video proxy CAM service backend is instantiated in the first network (CAM 1) from the Tenant Web Portal at the start of the experiment.
- After instantiation, both OBUs subscribed to the Integration Fabric (IF 1) receive a start-experiment signal. They will then process this signal to start logging and to get information about the video proxy CAM service deployment.
- OBU1 starts transmitting V2X messages (CAM=Cooperative Awareness Message), including the StationID, which is used both as identifier of the video stream, and as identifier for the PRAE to follow the V2X message of this car as trigger to determine when to instantiate the CAM service in the second network as the OBU1 approaches the border. All UEs subscribed to the suitable topic of the V2X Broker, receive the V2X message.
- the OBUs requests the IP address of the CAM 1 service from the Assisted Service Continuity (ASC 1) enabler to upload or request the video.
- OBU1 starts publishing video. OBU2 requests the video transmitted by OBU1 from the CAM 1 service.
- When approaching the border, PRAE instantiates the CAM service in the second network
- When OBU1 crosses the border, the video stream closes automatically due to network disruption.
- The OBU starts then polling the ASC enabler to get the IP of the video proxy instance CAM Service (CAM 2) in the second network.
- If an answer is received, the OBU is aware of the network change and will connect to the CAM service and the enablers in the second network.
- The OBU1 redirects the video stream to CAM service 2. OBU2 subscribes to the stream of CAM service 2.
- The UEs subscribe to the V2X broker and the Integration Fabric in the second network.

7.2 Testing of the interactions

In 2023, the laboratory trials for UC1.3 aimed to involve the verification of the technological enablers and the virtualization of the CAM Service backend (i.e., video server) at CTTC premises. To test the video proxy capabilities, the UC1.3 video proxy has been virtualized and onboarded as a virtualized CAM service inside the CAM Services Platforms instances available at CTTC laboratory. The process involved the creation of container images, Helm Chart descriptors and the creation of Open Source MANO (OSM) packages. Later, these artefacts are onboarded in the CTTC multi-administrative environment with the interaction of CAM Repository and Integration Fabric, as described in D2.1 [7] Section 4.3.2. Briefly, the CTTC environment consists of two servers, representing two administrative domains where there are computing resources (CPU, memory, storage,

networking) to run the enablers of the CAM Services Platform and the virtualized CAM Services backend instances used in the field trials. More details about this environment can be found in D2.9 [11] Section 3.2.4. The VPN used from VTT to CTTC allows interaction with both instances of the CAM Services Platform, one at each administrative domain. To simplify the whole process, all the deployed enabler's IP addresses have been hardcoded in the scripts.

To feed the V2X broker, a traffic generator has been used to send CAM messages and verify the exchange of messages between the two CAM Services Platform instances at CTTC experimental environment. In addition, this allows the PRAE enabler (not yet tested with UC1.3) to follow the position of the car registered as leader by the video proxy CAM service backend. The aim is that PRAE predicts when this leading car approaches a virtual border, to then trigger the instantiation of a new video proxy CAM service backend in a close point of presence of the other administrative domain. To indicate which car is pushing the video (the leader of the platoon), the car's stationID number is included inside the RTSP request to the CAM service. The latter, using a background process that checks the video server activity via a dedicated API, allows for the extraction of the car's StationID and subsequently pushes this information to the PRAE enabler.

The Assisted Service Continuity (ASC) enabler has been tested so that the video application scripts, before pushing and requesting the video stream from the CAM service, request beforehand the IP address of the video proxy CAM service from the ASC. To recreate the disconnection effect from the service without unplugging Ethernet cables or 5G interfaces at VTT premises, the dedicated VPN process used to connect to CTTC has been stopped and restarted. When the VPN connection drops, the video application processes running at the two UEs (one pushing the video and the other requesting it) automatically stop and continuously start polling the ASC enabler (the instance placed in the second CTTC administrative domain) to get the CAM service IP address running in a point of presence of the second administrative domain. In addition, when recovering the signal, both UEs start subscribing to the Integration Fabric (IF) and V2X broker instances of the CAM Services Platform in the new domain. To inform the UEs to initiate the logging processes, the UEs receive a message to start and stop logging coming from the IF. This message is normally triggered by the Tenant Web Portal (TWP) when the experiment starts or stops. Hence, the TWP signals to the UE via its graphical user interface when to start/stop the collection of measurements. At the end of the test, both UEs process their Qosium results offline and upload the data to TWP for visualization through its available APIs.

Figure 72: Basic workflow of UC1.3 interaction with available enablers of CAM Services Platform